

Polifonia: a digital harmoniser for musical heritage knowledge, H2020

**D4.6: Software for knowledge extraction from text – context – 2nd version
(V1.0)**

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3	KCL	KING'S COLLEGE LONDON	United Kingdom
4	NUI GALWAY	NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF IRELAND GALWAY	Ireland
5	MiC	MINISTERIO DELLA CULTURA	Italy
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7	CNAM	CONSERVATOIRE NATIONAL DES ARTS ET METIERS	France
8	NISV	STICHTING NEDERLANDS INSTITUUT VOOR BEELD EN GELUID	Netherlands
9	KNAW	KONINKLIJKE NEDERLANDSE AKADEMIE VAN WETEN- SCHAPPEN	Netherlands
10	DP	DIGITAL PATHS	Italy

Project Summary

European musical heritage is a dynamic historical flow of experiences, leaving heterogeneous traces that are difficult to capture, connect, access, interpret, and valorise. Computing technologies have the potential to shed a light on this wealth of resources by extracting, materialising and linking new knowledge from heterogeneous sources, hence revealing facts and experiences from hidden voices of the past. Polifonia makes this happen by building novel ways of inspecting, representing, and interacting with digital content. Memory institutions, scholars, and citizens will be able to navigate, explore, and discover multiple perspectives and stories about European Musical Heritage.

Polifonia focuses on European Musical Heritage, intended as musical contents and artefacts - or music objects - (tunes, scores, melodies, notations, etc.) along with relevant knowledge about them such as: their links to tangible objects (theatres, conservatoires, churches, etc.), their cultural and historical contexts, opinions and stories told by people having diverse social and artistic roles (scholars, writers, students, intellectuals, musicians, politicians, journalists, etc), and facts expressed in different styles and disciplines (memoire, reportage, news, biographies, reviews), different languages (English, Italian, French, Spanish, and German), and across centuries.

The overall goal of the project is to realise an ecosystem of computational methods and tools supporting discovery, extraction, encoding, interlinking, classification, exploration of, and access to, musical heritage knowledge on the Web. An equally important objective is to demonstrate that these tools improve the state of the art of Social Science and Humanities (SSH) methodologies. Hence their development is guided by, and continuously intertwined with, experiments and validations performed in real-world settings, identified by musical heritage stakeholders (both belonging to the Consortium and external supporters) such as cultural institutes and collection owners, historians of music, anthropologists and ethnomusicologists, linguists, etc.

Executive Summary

Deliverable D4.6, Software for knowledge extraction from text – context – 2nd version, presents the second release of knowledge extraction models of the Polifonia project. The task of knowledge extraction, especially when it is concerned with historical documents, is particularly complex and difficult. The historical nature of the Polifonia project, that deals with the preservation and promotion of musical heritage, poses serious challenges to the analysis of textual documents. Even though, in recent years Natural Language Processing (NLP) has witnessed many progress, first with the introduction of the transformer architecture [1] and then with the use of this architecture to develop Large Language Models (LLM) such as ChatGPT [2], these progresses are mainly focused on the analysis of contemporary and clean documents. By contrast, the documents collected and organized by the Polifonia project¹ [3] are historical and from different sources, such as OCR processed periodicals and books. The first challenge posed by the historical nature of the material is related with linguistic variations. In fact, if we want to use a pre-trained language model to encode the words in a sentence, it will be difficult for it to deal with words or syntactic structures never seen in contemporary internet documents. The situation can get even worse if in addition to linguistic variations we have to deal also with OCR errors that can cause unexpected behaviour in LLM, usually trained on clean text. Furthermore, another variable that hinders the reuse of recent NLP models is the different distribution of entities in historical and contemporary texts. State-of-the-art NLP models for entity linking, the task of associating a mention in a text with the description of this mention in a knowledge base such as Wikipedia, is different and can cause the linker to produce inconsistent associations, linking, for example, the mention of a person in a XVIII century book with an entity that lived in XX century, only because the training set used by this model contains more references to contemporary entity than to historical ones [4] or because the reference knowledge base does not contain minor historical entities. Taking all these issues into account, in this deliverable we improved our knowledge extraction pipeline (Polifonia Knowledge Extractor²) under different aspects:

- presenting Text2AMR2FRED, a text-to-Knowledge Graph (KG) pipeline that transforms multilingual natural language text into OWL-compliant RDF Knowledge Graphs (Section 2);
- improving the quality of text by developing a new set of models for the correction of OCR errors in historical documents (Section 3);
- creating a new benchmark for the evaluation of entity linking models, centered on historical OCRed document and on the music domain;
- developed a new time-aware model for historical entity linking that will replace the general entity linker of our pipeline (Section 4).

All these improvements will contribute to the general goal of WP4: making musical heritage knowledge available through dedicated knowledge graphs that can be easily queried. The produced models have been all evaluated on standard and *ad-hoc* benchmarks with good results and will continue to be under analysis until the end of the project, when we will release our final deliverable that deals with the development of methodologies and tools to evaluate knowledge extraction methods.

¹<https://polifonia disi.unibo.it/corpus/>

²<https://github.com/polifonia-project/Polifonia-Knowledge-Extractor>

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1. General Introduction

This report describes the work developed within Polifonia Work Package 4 (WP4). This Work Package (WP) aims to provide the project and its pilots with methods and tools to extract Musical Heritage (MH) knowledge from text. During the project, we dedicated an initial focus to building and evaluating a multilingual textual corpus on MH (Task 4.1), the Polifonia Textual Corpus [3]. This large corpus represents the source of information that we are extracting and organizing to develop tools that can guarantee the preservation of musical heritage knowledge and easy access to it. To this end, we released tools for the automatic linguistic annotation of texts [5], data [3] and an interface to interrogate the content of the corpus¹. Regarding the organization of information into knowledge, we developed and released a full-fledged pipeline for knowledge extraction from text, the first version of the Polifonia Knowledge Extractor² (PKE). It allows the process of plain text and its transformation into semantic graph structures. The PKE was the focus of Deliverable 4.5, and with this deliverable (D4.6), we improved different aspects of its pipeline.

The new contributions brought to the PKE in this deliverable is an improved version of AMR2FRED³ [6], a software component that complements the PKE and allows the transformation of the AMR graphs into RDF Knowledge Graphs [7] compliant to FRED[8] theoretical model. The PKE and the AMR2FRED tools can be exploited jointly in the Text2AMR2FRED (API⁴ and WebApp⁵), a revised architecture of FRED's text-to-KG pipeline. Also, as a new contribution, we propose a methodology, matured within a Proof-of-Concept study, to compare knowledge extraction capabilities between our text-to-KG pipeline and latest generation Large Language Models [2].

Other interventions on the PKE were also necessary because we realized how complex and difficult it is to deal with historical and multilingual documents during the unfolding of the project. The field of Natural Language Processing is mainly focused on the present, and the development of new models and benchmarks needs to consider the fact that language analysis could also be performed on historical documents that vary in terms of linguistic features, style and quality. For this reason, we found the reuse of tools developed for modern languages, trained on text written without spelling errors and in a stable style, extremely challenging and prone to errors. The main problems that affect the processing of historical documents in the PKE pipeline are related to OCR errors and the linking of mentions in text with entities described in a knowledge base such as WikiData. OCR errors cause unexpected errors in the text processor (text2AMR) of the PKE pipeline, with both loss of information, in case the model is not able to represent the affected sentence, and misinterpretation, in case an OCR error changes the form of a word with another acceptable word, e.g., *play* → *say*. We developed and evaluated new models for correcting OCR errors in different languages to overcome this problem.

Regarding entity linking, it is well known that modern language models applied for this task [9] have a *popularity bias* [10] that tends to associate an ambiguous mention in text with an entity that occurs often in a training set. Since the documents on which we are working differ from modern training sets for the task, based mainly on Wikipedia [11], we found that the employment of state-of-the-art entity linkers is sub-optimal. For this reason, we developed and evaluated new models for historical entity linking.

These improvements will contribute to increasing the PKE's accuracy. With this deliverable, we show that the new models that will be incorporated in the PKE pipeline are superior in terms of performance to the ones that we used in the first version of the framework and with the next deliverable D4.7 (Evaluation of multilingual corpora and knowledge extraction methods) we will quantify the improvements developing a benchmark for the task of knowledge extraction that unfortunately is still missing.

¹<https://polifonia.disi.unibo.it/corpus/>

²<https://github.com/polifonia-project/Polifonia-Knowledge-Extractor>

³<https://github.com/polifonia-project/amr2Fred>

⁴<http://framester.istc.cnr.it/txt-amr-fred/api/docs/>

⁵<https://arco.istc.cnr.it/txt-amr-fred/>

1.1. Structure of the Document and Contribution

This report is organized into an introduction and three chapters. Each chapter is self-contained and can be seen as a scientific article divided into an introduction, state-of-the-art, method, experimentals, analysis and conclusion. Chapter 2 describes the structural improvements to PKE and an initial evaluation of the pipeline against ChatGPT. Chapter 3 presents our work on OCR post-correction with developing new models, training sets and an extensive evaluation. Chapter 4 is about Historical Entity Linking. In this chapter, we will present a new benchmark for the task and a set of new models that can work on different periods and on different languages. Also, for this task, we provide an extensive evaluation.

The contribution of this deliverable can be summarized as follows:

- software components that complete the functionality of PKE, making it possible to transform plain text into full-fledged, OWL-compliant RDF Knowledge Graphs;
- a new small benchmark for the evaluation of knowledge extraction models;
- new models for OCR post-correction
- new silver training sets for OCR post-correction
- new benchmarks for historical entity linking
- new models for historical entity linking

All these improvements make PKE more accurate and allow us to focus now on its full evaluation that will be provided as the last deliverable of the WP4, Deliverable 4.7 (Evaluation of multilingual corpora and knowledge extraction methods). Enriching the field of knowledge extraction with a necessary resource for the task.

2. Text2AMR2Fred

2.1. Introduction

The vast collection of Musical Heritage documentary evidence in multiple languages (English, German, Dutch, French, Italian, Spanish) collected in the Polifonia Textual Corpus (PTC)¹ represents a mine of insights retrievable at scale through Knowledge Extraction. The Knowledge Extraction task can be framed and performed as transforming unstructured text into Knowledge Graphs (KGs). This transformation facilitates the structured and formally sound representation of implicit and explicit relationships within the text, offering a semantically rich visualization of the underlying information.

Natural Language Processing (NLP) and Semantic Web (SW) communities dedicated significant effort to text-to-KG pipelines. The NLP community exploited the progress of Machine Learning (ML) to address the challenges of semantic parsing [12], such as (i) representing the concepts occurring in a text unambiguously; (ii) being grounded in external knowledge bases, enabling computational inference, so to combine meanings to access supplementary knowledge; (iii) being flexible enough to encompass the variability of natural languages and robust to out-of-distribution phenomena.

Semantic parsing can be shallow, as in the task of Semantic Role Labeling [13], which identifies the predicates in a sentence and connects them with their semantic roles. Instead, deep semantic parsing produces a precise meaning representation of utterances that can contain significant compositionality, including relations among predicates and temporal information. This is the case of graph-based semantic parsing, which has gained attention due to the potential of general-purpose representations, such as Abstract Meaning Representation [14, AMR]. Text-to-AMR transduction based on neural machine translation and sequence-to-sequence (*seq2seq*) models achieved promising results both in scenarios limited to English and AMR parsing ([15, SPRING], Transition-based AMR parsing [16]) and in multi-language and multi-formalisms scenarios ([17, SGL]). However, neural semantic parsers struggle with making the extracted knowledge interoperable and exploitable due to its formalisms' heterogeneity (also referred to as *balkanisation*) [18] and not formally sound logic.

The SW provides means to formally represent the extracted knowledge according to interoperable ontologies, therefore favouring knowledge augmentation with heterogeneous Knowledge Bases (KBs) and alignment with other ontologies. An example is the SW machine reader [8, FRED], which encodes the extracted information using Semantic Web (SW) standards. The resulting KGs enable the exploration and retrieval of facts extracted from heterogeneous text corpora through structured queries and their augmentation through alignment to other KGs by leveraging [19, Framester], a semantic hub of various lexical knowledge bases. This alignment supports disclosing explicit knowledge that would otherwise remain hidden in texts. However, FRED relies on cumbersome NLP pipelines, which are hard to maintain and unsuitable to scale in multilingual scenarios.

On the other hand, latest generation Large Language Models (LLMs, [20]) have shown capabilities of generating human-like text and performing various tasks that are at the fulcrum of knowledge extraction/retrieval, such as semantic parsing (Semantic Role Labelling [21], AMR parsing [15] [16] [17], and others) However, there are concerns regarding their reliability in downstream applications such as Question Answering (QA). These concerns are especially valid for historical documents, which might be under-represented in LLMs training data, primarily made of web-crawled content, such as [22], [23], [24]. Retrieving knowledge from such documents could be more challenging due to the reluctance of LLMs to retain knowledge that rarely appears in their training datasets [4]. We hypothesise that employing neuro-symbolic text-to-KG pipelines to construct Knowledge Graphs (KGs) from textual data can result in more accurate and controllable knowledge extraction, refractory to hallucinations and to the spread of false but truthful information.

¹<https://github.com/polifonia-project/Polifonia-Corpus>

In this section of this deliverable, we recapitulate the main features of Polifonia Knowledge Extractor² in Section 2.2. In Section 2.3, we present Text2AMR2FRED (API⁴ and WebApp⁵), a revolutionised architecture of FRED's text-to-KG pipeline. This section also reports the adoption and application of Text2AMR2FRED⁵ by text-based pilots. In Section 2.4, we first summarise the evaluation procedures implemented within the work done for the previous Deliverable ([25]). Then, we report on the new experimental methodology and initial findings to compare knowledge extraction capabilities between our pipeline and Large Language Models. We aim to identify strengths and weaknesses in both approaches and explore the potential for a hybrid framework that merges NLP/NLU and Semantic Web elements.

2.2. Knowledge Extraction Pipeline D4.5 - Text2AMR

Deliverable 4.5 [25] focused on the development of Polifonia Knowledge Extractor (PKE)². Through PKE, we released an AMR graphs bank focused on the music domain³, containing text from contemporary and historical documentary sources. PKE² relies on AMR parsing as an intermediate step for extracting knowledge from diachronic corpora. AMR graphs, grounded in PropBank *Frames*⁴ [26], serve as an intermediate event-centric representation, well-suited for retrieving the essential elements of a situation described in a text, such as who or what took a particular action and who or what underwent the consequences of a particular event. The advantage of AMR representation of meaning is detaching from syntax variability and word-forms, providing the same graph for sentences having the same semantics but a different syntactic realisation. The text-to-AMR parsing module of (PKE)² relies on the neural semantic parsers [15, SPRING] for English and [27, USEA] for languages other than English.

The main novelty and impact of the PKE implementation and the AMR graphs bank release revolves around designing a new methodology for extracting knowledge from contemporary and historical text. The methodology implements tools and techniques for minimising the loss of information in the source text by performing co-reference resolution⁵ and OCR post-correction⁶.

The methodology designed in Deliverable 4.5 [25] is completed by the new contributions described in this deliverable (as reported in Section 2.3) to finally contribute to the modelling and population of the Polifonia Knowledge Graph. The knowledge harvested through AMR parsing and harmonised in the Polifonia Knowledge Graph is intended to enable advanced QA based on Persona's⁷ competency questions and KG modelling constraints designed by WP1 and WP2 and explained in Deliverable 1.1 [28], and Deliverables 2.1 and 2.3 [29] [30]. The work performed within WP4 and for Deliverable 4.5 probed SotA AMR parsers on historical documents, which for those parsers are out-of-domain, stylistically different from documents in their training sets.

2.3. New contributions

2.3.1. Text2AMR2FRED at work

The work carried out within Deliverable 4.5 [25] evolved until contributing to the development of an enhanced version of AMR2FRED³. AMR2FRED is a tool that exploits similarities between AMR and FRED's graphs, such as being frame-based and event-centric, to transform AMR graphs into RDF/OWL KGs that follow FRED's theoretical model. PKE² and AMR2FRED tools lay the basis for our text-to-KG framework. The framework can be invoked via the Ma-

²<https://github.com/polifonia-project/Polifonia-Knowledge-Extractor>

³Available at <https://zenodo.org/record/7025779#.ZDls8OxBy3I>

⁴PropBank Frames are the core lexicon of the PropBank paradigm and consist of predicate-argument structures named "rolesets". A complete list of PropBank frames can be found at: <http://propbank.github.io/v3.4.0/frames/>

⁵For English language documents, we implemented a co-reference resolution pipeline based on Spacy's *neuralcoref* (<https://spacy.io/universe/project/neuralcoref>). We are currently evaluating tools for languages other than English.

⁶Our initial approach to OCR post-correction is a rule-based method detailed at <https://github.com/polifonia-project/rulebased-postocr-corrector>. It targets sentence cohesion issues, particularly those caused by historical periodicals' peculiar formats, like multiple columns leading to incorrect sentence breaks.

⁷<https://polifonia-project.github.io/ecosystem/personas.html>

Figure 2.1: Overview of the hybrid text-to-KG framework proposed in this research.

chine Reading suite⁸, which exploits the Text-to-AMR-to-FRED API⁹ to obtain RDF *named graphs* [31] produced by using the N-Quad¹⁰ syntax. Named graphs allow for extending the standard RDF triple model with a "context" element which, among the other features, allows the association of each triple with information about their provenance. In our case, the context element of the triples indicates which sentence's graph the triple is part of.

Figure 2.1 depicts the various steps of our framework.

Figure 2.2: Graph resulting from the text2AMR parsing powered by [15, SPRING] of the sentence *Apple unveils revolutionary watch* obtained via Text2AMR2FRED WebApp.

Figure 2.3: Graph resulting from the AMR2FRED translation powered by AMR2FRED of the sentence *Apple unveils revolutionary watch* obtained via Text2AMR2FRED WebApp.

The resulting RDF/OWL KGs can be finally enriched through Framester¹¹, an extensive KG that interlinks diverse

⁸available at: <https://github.com/polifonia-project/machine-reading>

⁹Available at: <http://framester.istc.cnr.it/txt-amr-fred/api/docs>

¹⁰<https://www.w3.org/TR/n-quads/>

¹¹<https://github.com/framester/Framester>

lexical and ontological resources such as FrameNet¹², WordNet¹³, VerbNet¹⁴, VerbAtlas¹⁵, BabelNet¹⁶, DBPedia¹⁷, Yago¹⁸, DOLCE-Zero¹⁹ and other resources. Framester facilitates KGs enrichment by, for example, enabling the addition of semantics to the generic argument slots of PropBank⁴ predicates as found in AMR graphs. Specifically, the "ARG0-PAG" argument of the "play.11" predicate can, through Framester, be formally associated with a persistent URI²⁰. For example, the output KGs are enriched through Word Sense Disambiguation (WSD) based on the RDF version of WordNet [32], included in Framester. WordNet [33] is a lexical Knowledge Base that groups words through synonymy relation into sets called synsets, linked to each other through other semantic relationships, such as hyponymy, meronymy, etc. In our pipeline, the WSD process is applied to AMR elements (usually nouns and adjectives) that miss links to lexical resources. Figure 2.2 shows the AMR graph corresponding to the sentence "Apple unveils revolutionary watch". The reader may notice that predicates in AMR graphs are associated with PropBank word senses and Named Entities are associated with their corresponding entities in Wikipedia. The node `z3 / watch` instead is missing a link to lexical resources. Therefore, we disambiguate it against Framester. The WSD process consists of submitting the original sentence to EWISER²¹, a WSD system well-suited for multilingual scenarios due to its SotA performance in both all-words English WSD and multilingual WSD tasks. As Figure 2.3 shows, we associate the result of WSD (WordNet's synsets) with the AMR nodes missing links to any external source and whose label corresponds to the lemma of the input sentence. This association is implemented through the `owl:equivalentClass` property between the identified node and the selected WordNet's synset in Framester. For the example above, we use EWISER and keep the information for the lemma "watch". For the same entities (those not linked with external information sources), we further exploit Framester to generate alignments to two top-level ontologies: WordNet "supersenses" (through the `rdfs:subclassOf` property) and a subset of DOLCE+DnS Ultra Lite (DUL) classes.

2.3.2. Adoption and application by text-based Pilots

Text-based Polifonia pilots can leverage Text2AMR2FRED to extract structured knowledge from their collection of textual documents and meet their requirements.

For example, our framework was applied to a module of PTC¹⁵, the *MusicBO* pilot's corpus²², focusing on a selection of documents in English and Italian. The resulting MusicBO Knowledge Graph is available on GitHub²³ and through a public SPARQL endpoint²⁴. Data stories extracted from it are published on MELODY²⁵. Through MELODY, it is possible to visualise the SPARQL queries used to interrogate the MusicBO KG endpoint and build the published stories. We extensively described MusicBO Knowledge Graph in Deliverable 2.3 [30].

Other text-based Pilots, such as *ORGANS*, *BELLS*, *MEETUPS* and *CHILD*, can exploit our Text2KG pipeline to transform the unstructured information contained in their collection of textual documents into structured knowledge. The usage of the tool presented in Sub-section 2.3.1 of this report is eased and streamlined by its APIs and other support tools, such as the Machine Reading suite⁸, listed in Sub-section 2.6.

While the experimental focus is on the Musical Heritage (MH) domain, our results and methods are generalisable and applicable to any arbitrary collection of texts. This research will enable scholars, e.g. musicologists, to access historical and multilingual sources more widely and easily.

¹²<https://framenet.icsi.berkeley.edu/fndrupal/>

¹³<https://wordnet.princeton.edu/>

¹⁴<https://verbs.colorado.edu/verbnet/>

¹⁵<https://verbatlas.org/>

¹⁶<https://babelnet.org/>

¹⁷<https://www.dbpedia.org/>

¹⁸<https://www.mpi-inf.mpg.de/departments/databases-and-information-systems/research/yago-naga/yago/>

¹⁹<http://www.ontologydesignpatterns.org/ont/d0.owl>

²⁰<https://w3id.org/framester/pb/data/role/play-11/performer>

²¹<https://github.com/SapienzaNLP/ewiser>

²²MusicBO pilot's corpus collects documents regarding the role of music in the cultural heritage history of Bologna.

²³<https://github.com/polifonia-project/musicbo-knowledge-graph>

²⁴<https://polifonia.disi.unibo.it/musicbo/sparql>

²⁵https://projects.dharc.unibo.it/melody/musicbo/music_in_bologna_knowledge_graph_overview

2.4. Evaluation

2.4.1. AMR graphs - Automatic Filtering

Table 2.1: Automatic filtering analytics of EN and ITA documents' sentences of MusicBO corpus

Corpus	Lan	#sents (Tot.)	#sents (Post-filtering)
MusicBO	EN	51.814	5.965(0, 11)
	ITA	10.563	1.815(0, 17)

We implemented several evaluation procedures as part of PKE². In fact, given that we are concentrating on non-standard texts (historical documents) as input texts, we expect the results of SotA AMR parsers to be potentially inaccurate. Human validation is time-consuming, and there are no standard benchmarks for the semantic parsing of historic and OCRed text. The future work that we will perform for our final deliverable (D4.7 Evaluation of multilingual corpora and knowledge extraction methods) will focus on creating resources for the evaluation of the tool.

First, we implemented an automatic filtering step. We leveraged a back-translation approach [34] and converted the generated AMR graphs back to sentences (AMR2Text) to compute similarity scores between the original sentence and the generated one. For English, we used [15, SPRING] for AMR2Text generation and computed [35, BLEURT]²⁶ as a similarity score. For languages other than English, we used [36, m-AMR2Text] for AMR2Text generation, and we computed the cosine similarity between the original and the generated sentence embeddings. We generated the embeddings through [37, LASER embeddings]²⁷, a multilingual sentence embedding toolkit. We hypothesise that generated sentences with high BLEURT (for English sentences) and cosine similarity (for other-than-English sentences) scores correspond to high-quality graphs. In fact, according to the qualitative sample-checks we did to perform error analysis, negative BLEURT scores and low cosine similarity corresponded to low-quality original sentences, severely affected by issues such as OCR errors. In turn, low-quality sentences correspond to unsatisfactory quality AMR graphs. Consequently, we decided to discard all the AMR graphs corresponding to AMR2Text-generated sentences with (relatively) low BLEURT or cosine similarity scores. A negative BLEURT score or a cosine similarity <.9. In fact, according to our sample-based qualitative error analysis, negative BLEURT scores (<0) and relatively low cosine similarity (<0.9) corresponded to low-quality generated sentences and, consequentially, to low-quality AMR graphs (graphs whose input sentences were affected, for example, by severe OCR errors). The discarded sentence-AMR graph pairs are not part of the final AMR graphs bank²⁸ and are not promoted to be transformed into RDF/OWL KGs.

On the one hand, opting for a back-translation strategy, facilitated by the AMR parsers' ability to execute the AMR2Text task, permits the automatic exclusion of lower-quality AMR graphs. On the other hand, this technique is constrained by the accuracy of the AMR2Text model. We find these limitations acceptable, as they enable us to adopt a conservative approach and, in the least favorable circumstance, risk losing high-quality information without retaining low-quality data.

The impact of the application of the automatic filtering strategies can be described by discussing the case-study of MusicBO KG creation^{23,24}. For creating MusicBO KG, we applied Text2AMR2FRED to a subset of MusicBO corpus, made of 47 documents in English and 51 documents in Italian, whose publication dates span from 1700 to the current era. For the sentences extrapolated from the English documents, we decided to discard all the AMR graphs corresponding to AMR2Text-generated sentences with a negative BLEURT score. For the Italian documents, we decided to discard all the AMR graphs corresponding to AMR2Text-generated sentences' embeddings with a cosine similarity <0.90. In fact, according to our sample-based qualitative error analysis, negative BLEURT scores and cosine similarity <0.90 corresponded to low-quality generated sentences and, consequentially, to low-quality AMR

²⁶<https://github.com/google-research/bleurt>

²⁷<https://github.com/yannvgn/laserembeddings>

²⁸Available at <https://zenodo.org/record/7025779#.ZDls80xBy3I>

graphs (graphs whose input sentences were affected, for example, by severe OCR errors). For Italian, we have been able to keep 17% of the total sentences. For English, we have been able to keep 11% of the total sentences. The discarded sentence-AMR graph pairs were not transformed into RDF/OWL KGs and are not part of MusicBO KG.

2.4.2. AMR graphs - Human Qualitative Analysis

Figure 2.4: A screenshot taken from the AMR Evaluation WebApp, showing an example of a predicate node’s Propbank frame and core role assessments.

To validate the automatic filtering, we have developed a web tool²⁹ to support human qualitative analysis of the graphs. In fact, BLEURT score and cosine similarity calculation are thought to be used in combination with human evaluation guided by the notion of *Motifs* [38], basic non-reducible *boxes* of semantic information. In [38], the authors identify 9 motifs that can be identified in FRED [8] graphs. We ran a preliminary analysis to assess the feasibility of mapping the motifs reported in [38] to AMR graphs’ core and non-core roles. Mapping AMR nodes, core and non-core roles to already identified and possibly new *Motifs* will potentially guide us to find a correlation between the scores and human judgement. We believe that correlating the scores to qualitative insights collected through human evaluation could lead us to identify a BLEURT/cosine similarity score *lower bound* upon which AMR graphs can be considered of satisfactory quality also from a human validation perspective.

We are not yet in the position of calculating and sharing any metrics obtained through the human evaluation task. This is in fact the objective of Deliverable 4.7, the final WP4 deliverable. Nevertheless, in Deliverable 4.5 [25] we shared an in-depth analysis of the process through examples of human assessment given on a sentence taken from the PTC¹. An example is reported in Figure 2.4. We also shared a proposal for human validation scoring criteria, a first scoring system proposal, which is based on calculating the percentage of assessments given which value is "correct" over the total assessments that can be assigned in a given AMR graph.

²⁹<http://framester.istc.cnr.it/amr-eval>

2.4.3. Comparison with Large Language Models - Proof-of-Concept Study

Figure 2.5: ChatGPT's answer to the question "Who composed *Die Zaubergeige*?"

2.4.3.1. Background

We expect Large Language Models to be potentially unreliable in downstream tasks like Question Answering (QA) due to their sensitivity to prompting, hallucinations and disinclination to retain long-tail knowledge, namely knowledge that rarely appears in their training datasets [4]. The work described in this Section is driven by the hypothesis that building Knowledge Graphs (KGs) from text through a neuro-symbolic text-to-KG pipeline can give higher control over the knowledge extracted, mitigating the risks of hallucinations and the retrieval of false but truthful information.

For example, Figure 2.5 shows the answer provided by GPT3.5 interrogated via the free online version of ChatGPT³⁰ to the question "Who composed *Die Zaubergeige*?". The answer provided by ChatGPT is wrong, as it can be verified against *Die Zaubergeige* Wikipedia page³¹. Instead, by running a SPARQL query that we report in example 2.4.3.1) on the KG obtained through Text2AMR2FRED API⁴ and WebApp⁵ from the Wikipedia page's text³², that we report in example 2.1, we can reliably obtain the correct answer, namely Werner Egk.

```
SPARQL query to answer the question "Who composed \textit{Die Zaubergeige}?"
PREFIX fred: <http://www.ontologydesignpatterns.org/ont/fred/domain.owl#>
PREFIX pb: <https://w3id.org/framester/pb/localrole/>
```

³⁰<https://chat.openai.com/>

³¹https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Die_Zaubergeige

³²*Die Zaubergeige* is a 1935 opera by Werner Egk to a libretto by Ludwig Strecker after Count Franz Pocci. Egk revised the opera in 1954.

```

SELECT ?composer
WHERE {
    ?composeActivity pb:entity_composed fred:Die_Zaubergerige .
    ?composeActivity pb:artist ?composer .
}
    
```

Listing 2.1: KG obtained via Text2AMR2FRED³² from *Die Zaubergerige* Wikipedia page text⁴

```

@prefix amr: <http://www.ontologydesignpatterns.org/ont/amr/> .
@prefix amrb: <http://www.ontologydesignpatterns.org/ont/amrb/> .
@prefix boxer: <http://www.ontologydesignpatterns.org/ont/boxer/boxer.owl#> .
@prefix dbpedia: <http://dbpedia.org/resource/> .
@prefix dul: <http://www.ontologydesignpatterns.org/ont/dul/DUL.owl#> .
@prefix fred: <http://www.ontologydesignpatterns.org/ont/fred/domain.owl#> .
@prefix fschema: <https://w3id.org/framester/schema/> .
@prefix owl: <http://www.w3.org/2002/07/owl#> .
@prefix pbdata: <https://w3id.org/framester/pb/data/> .
@prefix pblr: <https://w3id.org/framester/pb/localrole/> .
@prefix rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#> .
@prefix va: <http://verbatlas.org/> .
@prefix vn.role: <http://www.ontologydesignpatterns.org/ont/vn/abox/role/vnrole.owl#> .
@prefix wd: <http://www.Wikidata.org/entity/> .
@prefix wn30: <https://w3id.org/framester/wn/wn30/instances/> .
@prefix wn30schema: <https://w3id.org/framester/wn/wn30/schema/> .
@prefix xsd: <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#> .

fred:compose_1 a pbdata:compose-02 ;
    pblr:artist fred:Werner_Egk ;
    pblr:entity_composed fred:Die_Zaubergerige ;
    fschema:subsumedUnder va:0382f .

fred:have-org-role_1 a pbdata:have-org-role-91 ;
    pblr:office_holder fred:Franz_Pocci ;
    pblr:title_of_office_held fred:count_1 .

fred:include_1 a pbdata:include-91 ;
    pblr:subset fred:Die_Zaubergerige ;
    pblr:superset fred:opera_1 .

fred:libretto_1 a pbdata:libretto-01 ;
    boxer:agent fred:Ludwig_Strecker ;
    boxer:patient fred:opera_1 ;
    dul:hasQuality fred:After ;
    vn.role:Time fred:Franz_Pocci .

fred:revise_1 a pbdata:revise-01 ;
    vn.role:Time fred:date-entity_2 ;
    pblr:causer_of_transformation fred:Egk ;
    pblr:thing_changing fred:opera_2 ;
    fschema:subsumedUnder va:0091f .

fred:Egk a amr:Person ;
    owl:sameAs dbpedia:Helmut_Egk .

fred:Ludwig_Strecker a amr:Person ;
    
```

```
owl:sameAs dbpedia:Ludwig_Strecker,
  wd:Q1875079 .

fred:Werner_Egk a amr:Person ;
  owl:sameAs dbpedia:Werner_Egk,
  wd:Q458775 .

fred:count_1 a fred:Count .

fred:date-entity_1 a amr:Date-entity ;
  amrb:year 1935.0 .

fred:date-entity_2 a amr:Date-entity ;
  amrb:year 1954.0 .

fred:opera_2 a fred:Opera .

pbdata:compose-02 rdfs:label "to create, produce art" ;
  rdfs:subClassOf dul:Event .

pbdata:have-org-role-91 rdfs:subClassOf dul:Event .

pbdata:include-91 rdfs:subClassOf dul:Event .

pbdata:revise-01 rdfs:label "change, modify" ;
  rdfs:subClassOf dul:Event .

wn30:synset-opera-noun-1 wn30:schema:gloss "a drama set to music; consists of singing with
  orchestral accompaniment and an orchestral overture and interludes"@en-us .

fred:Die_Zauberberge a amr:Opera ;
  vn.role:Time fred:date-entity_1 ;
  owl:sameAs dbpedia:Die_Zauberberge,
  wd:Q1217683 .

fred:Franz_Pocci a amr:Person ;
  owl:sameAs dbpedia:Franz_Potocci .

fred:Opera rdfs:subClassOf dul:InformationEntity,
  wn30:supersense-noun_communication ;
  owl:equivalentClass wn30:synset-opera-noun-1 .

fred:opera_1 a fred:Opera .
```

The SPARQL query reported in the Example 2.4.3.1), used to interrogate the KG output by Text2AMR2FRED, can be built by consulting the AMR2FRED matrices³³ that document how PropBank's predicates and roles are transformed into FRED graphs relations' labels and mapped to Framenet and VerbAtlas KBs.

We implemented the Proof-of-Concept version of an experimental method to compare the knowledge extracted through our Knowledge Extraction pipeline and through Large Language Models (LLMs). This endeavour is crucial to enhance our understanding of LLMs' capabilities and limitations and identify to which aspects we could bring the most value with a hybrid Knowledge Extraction framework at the crossroads of NLP/NLU and SW. The paragraphs in this subsection summarise the method developed and the preliminary results obtained. The output of our Proof-

³³<https://github.com/infovillasimius/amr2Fred/blob/master/amr2Fred/src/amr2fred/propbankframematrix.tsv>,
<https://github.com/infovillasimius/amr2Fred/blob/master/amr2Fred/src/amr2fred/propbankrolematrix.tsv>

of-Concept study is stored in its dedicated GitHub repository³⁴.

2.4.3.2. Method

Table 2.2: Text2AMR2FRED and LLMs - Example of *Question formulation, ChatGPT prompting, ChatGPT answer's collection and evaluation* results recording

Named entity's Wikipedia page	Gender	Human Evaluator's Question	Human Evaluator's Prompt	Human Evaluator's Answer	Sentence (from Wikipedia page) containing the answer	Is ChatGPT's answer correct?	ChatGPT's answer
Giovanni_Battista_Pergolesi	M	What is the original name of Giovanni Battista Pergolesi?	What is the original name of Giovanni Battista Pergolesi? Give a straight answer.	Giovanni Battista Draghi	Giovanni Battista Draghi ([...]; 4 January 1710 – 16 or 17 March 1736), often referred to as Giovanni Battista Pergolesi [...], was an Italian Baroque composer, violinist, and organist, leading exponent of the Baroque; he is considered one of the greatest Italian musicians of the first half of the 18th century and one of the most important representatives of the Neapolitan school.	Yes	The original name of Giovanni Battista Pergolesi is Giovanni Battista Draghi.
George_Frideric_Handel	M	Who was the headmaster of George Frideric Handel's Gymnasium?	Who was the headmaster of George Frideric Handel's Gymnasium? Give a straight answer.	Johann Praetorius	Early in his life Handel is reported to have attended the Gymnasium in Halle, where the headmaster, Johann Praetorius, was reputed to be an ardent musician.	No	Johann Zacharias Grundig was the headmaster of George Frideric Handel's gymnasium in Halle, Germany.
Mary_Ann_Paton	F	Where did Mary Ann Paton's sister Isabella make her début as a musician?	Where did Mary Ann Paton's sister Isabella make her début as a musician? Give a straight answer.	Covent Garden Theatre	She and her sisters received a good musical training: they were singers also, Isabella making her début at Mary Ann's benefit at Covent Garden Theatre, 1824, as Letitia Hardy, and Eliza sing at the Haymarket Theatre in 1833.	No	Isabella Paton made her début as a musician at the Covent Garden Theatre in London.
Teresina_Brambilla	F	How long was Teresina Brambilla's career as a musician?	How long was Teresina Brambilla's career as a musician? Give a straight answer.	25 years	Teresa "Teresina" Brambilla[a] (15 April 1845 – 1 July 1921) was an Italian soprano who sang in the major opera houses of Europe in a career spanning 25 years.	No	As of my last knowledge update in September 2021, there is no widely known or documented musician by the name of Teresina Brambilla in the public domain. Therefore, I cannot provide information about the length of her musical career. It's possible that she gained recognition after my last update or that she is not a prominent figure in the music world.

We framed the comparison experiment as a Question Answering task on named entities of type PERSON. We compared GPT3.5's free-text answers to natural language questions, sent as prompts via the free online version of ChatGPT³⁵, to AMR graphs produced by our Text2AMR2FRED Web App⁵.

³⁴<https://github.com/polifonia-project/llms-vs-specialised-knowledge>

³⁵<https://chat.openai.com/>

Table 2.3: Text2AMR2FRED and LLMs - Example of *Text2AMR semantic parsing and evaluation* results recording

Named entity's Wikipedia page	Gender	Human Evaluator's Question	Human Evaluator's Answer	Sentence	Does the AMR graph contain an answer to the question?	AMR subgraph containing (or not) the answer
Giovanni_Battista_Pergolesi	M	What is the original name of Giovanni Battista Pergolesi?	Giovanni Battista Draghi	Giovanni Battista Draghi ([...]; 4 January 1710 – 16 or 17 March 1736), often referred to as Giovanni Battista Pergolesi [...], was an Italian Baroque composer, violinist, and organist, leading exponent of the Baroque; he is considered one of the greatest Italian musicians of the first half of the 18th century and one of the most important representatives of the Neapolitan school.	Yes	z7/person : wiki"Giovanni_Evangelista_Draghi" : name(z8/name : opl"Giovanni" : op2"Battista" : op3"Draghi") : ARG1-of(z9/refer-01 : ARG2(z10/person : wiki"Giovanni_Battista_Pergolesi" : name(z11/name : opl"Giovanni" : op2"Battista" : op3"Pergolesi")))
George_Frideric_Handel	M	Who was the headmaster of George Frideric Handel's Gymnasium?	Johann Praetorius	Early in his life Handel is reported to have attended the Gymnasium in Halle, where the headmaster, Johann Praetorius, was reputed to be an ardent musician.	no	z4/sports-facility : wiki"Halle" : name(z5/name : opl"Halle") : location-of(z6/repute-01 : ARG1(z7/person : wiki"Johann_Praetorius" : name(z8/name : opl"Johann" : op2"Praetorius") : ARG0-of(z9/have-org-role-91 : ARG2(z10/headmaster))) : ARG2(z11/musician : mod(z12/ardent)))
Mary_Ann_Paton	F	Where did Mary Ann Paton's sister Isabella make her debut as a musician?	Covent Garden Theatre	She and her sisters received a good musical training: they were singers also, Isabella making her debut at Mary Ann's benefit at Covent Garden Theatre, 1824, as Letitia Hardy, and Eliza sing at the Haymarket Theatre in 1833.	No	z14/person : wiki"Isabella_Girardeau" : name(z15/name : opl"Isabella") : ARG0-of(z16/debut-01 : ARG1z14 : location(z17/benefit : beneficiary(z18/person : wiki"Mary_Ann_Davenport" : name(z19/name : opl"Mary" : op2"Ann"))) : location(z20/building : wiki"Royal_Opera_House" : name(z21/name : opl"Covent" : op2"Garden" : op3"Theatre")))
Teresina_Brambilla	F	How long was Teresina Brambilla's career as a musician?	25 years	Teresa "Teresina" Brambilla (15 April 1845 – 1 July 1921) was an Italian soprano who sang in the major opera houses of Europe in a career spanning 25 years.	Yes	z1/person : wiki"Teresa_Teresina_Brambilla" : name(z2/name : opl"Teresa") : op2"Teresina" : op3"Brambilla") : ARG0-of(z8/sing-01 : duration(z14/career : duration(z15/temporal-quantity : quant25 : unit(z16/year))))

The experiment was held in August 2023.

The experiment breaks down into two macro-steps. The first macro-step is described in the numbered list below:

1. *Question formulation, ChatGPT prompting, ChatGPT's answer collection and evaluation*
 - 1..a Human evaluators selected a named entity of type PERSON occurring in Musical Heritage Historical Named Entity Recognition, Classification and Linking benchmark (MHMERCL v0.1) ³⁶.
 - 1..b Human evaluators were instructed to maintain a 50-50 gender³⁷ distribution between the selected male and female named entities³⁸. As a result, half of the questions focused on male historical characters, and the other half on female historical characters;
 - 1..c Human evaluators accessed the selected person named entity's Wikipedia page;
 - 1..d Human evaluators asked a question related to the named entity chosen at step 1.a to GPT3.5 via the free

³⁶This dataset, extensively described in Section 4 of this report, comprises music periodicals whose publication dates range from 1823 to 1900. Therefore, the historical characters occurring in it are related to music and known to be active or alive in a period similar to the periodicals' publication dates range

³⁷In our study, we restrict to binary gender categories, which, although not reflecting real-world diversity, lets us move the first steps towards the definition of our Proof-of-Concept study method. We consider a *female* person named entity a historical character that is referred to, in its Wikipedia page, with the pronoun *she*, a *male* person named entity a historical figure who is referred to, in its Wikipedia page, with the pronoun *he*.

³⁸Due to the nature of the dataset they were extrapolated from (historical periodicals, whose dates range from 1823 to 1900), both female and male named entities could not belong to significantly different periods. This factor allowed us to mitigate any potential bias related to females being associated with a markedly different time frame compared to males, and vice-versa.

online version of ChatGPT³⁹ via a single prompt containing the question⁴⁰;

1.e Human evaluators assessed the correctness of the answer given by ChatGPT.

The human evaluators that carried out the experiments are University of Bologna’s Foreign Languages and Literature undergraduate students who received *ad hoc* training and carried it out as part of their bachelor’s degree curricular internship. They recorded the experiment’s results in a spreadsheet following the format as in the sample reported in Table 2.2.

The second macro-step is described in the list below:

2. *Text2AMR semantic parsing evaluation*

2.a The human evaluator transforms the sentence(s)⁴⁰ from the Wikipedia page that contains the answer to the question formulated at step 1.d into an AMR graph;

2.b The human evaluator assesses the semantic correctness of the AMR graph. The assumption is that if the AMR graph is semantically correct (namely, the predicates recognised by the Text2AMR parser and their arguments are correct), it will be translated into an RDF/OWL KG able to provide the correct answer to a question via a SPARQL query.

The human evaluators who conducted the experiments are NLP and SW scholars familiar with the AMR formalism. They recorded the experiment’s results in a spreadsheet following the format as in the sample reported in Table 2.3.

2.4.3.3. Results

Table 2.4: Experiment’s macro-step 1. (*Question formulation, ChatGPT prompting, ChatGPT answer’s collection and evaluation*) results

Named entity’s gender	Is ChatGPT’s answer correct?		Grand Total
	Yes	No	
F	11(0, 22)	39(0, 78)	50(1, 00)
M	24(0, 48)	26(0, 52)	50(1, 00)
Grand Total	35(0, 35)	65(0, 65)	100(1, 00)

Table 2.5: Experiment’s macro-step 2., *Text2AMR semantic parsing evaluation* results

Named entity’s gender	Does the AMR graph contain an answer to the question?		Grand Total
	Yes	No	
F	7(0, 70)	3(0, 30)	10(1, 00)
M	8(0, 80)	2(0, 20)	10(1, 00)
Grand Total	15(0, 75)	5(0, 25)	20(1, 00)

The results of the experiment’s macro-step 1., *Question formulation, ChatGPT prompting, ChatGPT’s answer collection and evaluation*, are reported in Table 2.4. Looking at the results, we can see that ChatGPT tend to return wrong answers more often when prompted with questions about female named entities. This observation might corroborate the hypotheses regarding gender bias in LLMs [39] and in KBs such as Wikipedia [40].

As this is a Proof-of-Concept study aimed at exploring the feasibility of the research approach of Text2AMR2FRED VS LLMs comparison, we opted for a smaller sample size for the experiment’s macro-step 2, as AMR graphs assessment is challenging and time-consuming. Results of the experiment’s macro-step 2., are reported in Table 2.5.

³⁹<https://chat.openai.com/>

⁴⁰The question had to be answerable with information retrievable in the Wikipedia page of reference, visited in step 1.c.

Table 2.6: ChatGPT answers' correctness VS AMR graphs informativeness - Comparison

Named entity's gender	Does the AMR graph contain an answer to the question?		Is ChatGPT's answer correct?		Grand Total
	Yes	No	Yes	No	
F	7(0, 70)	3(0, 30)	1(0, 10)	9(0, 90)	10(1, 00)
M	8(0, 80)	2(0, 20)	2(0, 20)	8(0, 80)	10(1, 00)
Grand Total	15 (0,75)	5(0, 25)	3(0, 15)	17(0, 85)	20(1, 00)

Although the small sample size is a limitation of this Proof-of-Concept study, especially for the experiment's macro-step 2, it is noteworthy that answers are included in the AMR graphs, without apparent major bias toward the gender of the entities involved.

Table 2.6 shows a comparison between the ChatGPT answers' correctness and the AMR graphs informativeness (namely the presence, in the graph, of the answer to the question or not). The AMR graphs are produced according to experiment's macro-step 2 methodology. The comparison was performed on a random sub-sample of 20 questions asked about 20 person named entities, extrapolated from the sample collected in Experiment's macro-step 1. In spite of the constraints imposed by a small sample size, the table shows that the AMR graphs effectively capture the answers to the questions 75% of the times, while ChatGPT's answer is correct 15% of the times.

2.4.3.4. Future work

In future work, we plan to quantitatively expand the samples of the experiment whose Proof-of-Concept's methods and results are described in paragraph 2.4.3.2. We aim to expand the experiment's methodology more broadly and examine the interplay between gender and popularity bias along the lines of recent investigations by [4], [10] and push forward the research regarding LLMs struggle with long-tail knowledge [4]. Also, we plan to expand the experiment's macro-step 2 by building SPARQL queries to verify the informativeness of the Text2AMR2FRED OWL-compliant RDF output KGs through structured interrogations.

2.5. Conclusion

In this chapter, we presented Text2AMR2FRED, a tool that effectively mitigates the issues of existing NLP semantic parsers and machine readers. Adhering to Semantic Web standards to ensure interoperable knowledge extraction, it enhances the informativeness of KGs by aligning them with domain-specific ontologies, enabling interrogation through structured queries. Its approach uncovers implicit knowledge from text, enabling output KGs augmentation with external KBs.

In Section 2.2, we summarised the background work that made Text2AMR2FRED tool implementation possible. In Section 2.3, we highlighted the novel characteristics brought to Text2AMR2FRED within the work done for this deliverable (cfr. Sub-section 2.3.1). Also, we reported how text-based Polifonia pilots can leverage the structured knowledge Text2AMR2FRED extracts from unstructured text to meet their requirements (cfr. Sub-section 2.3.2). In particular, we described the creation and utility of the MusicBO pilot's KG, developed through a specific Knowledge Extraction pipeline and hosted on a public SPARQL endpoint. The KG's statistics and data stories²⁵, also outlined herein, suggest potential applications in advancing academic research, particularly in musicology.

In Section 2.4, we described the steps taken so far towards the evaluation of Text2AMR2FRED tool, in terms of AMR graphs automatic filtering methodologies (cfr. Sub-section 2.4.1) and human qualitative analysis (cfr. Sub-section 2.4.2). We have also described a Proof-of-Concept experiment for comparing the efficacy of our Knowledge Extraction pipeline with information retrieved by interrogating the free online version of ChatGPT, setting the ground for a methodology to compare the quality of the information stored by our Text2KG pipeline to that retrievable via asking questions to LLMs.

In future work, we aim to expand the current evaluation process by strengthening the integration of automatic metrics and human assessment. The enhancement of the latter will entail musicologists formulating domain-specific questions that will be transformed into SPARQL queries. These experts will then evaluate the output of these queries, providing a more robust understanding of the KG's effectiveness and areas for improvement.

Our evaluation method will be completed by the analysis of *Motifs*, basic logical patterns employed in SW, defined in [38], in the output KGs. The *Motifs*-based validation will permit a cross-tools knowledge extraction tasks comparative evaluation, following the method outlined in [41].

Lastly, it will be key to establish solid comparison pipelines between AMR-driven frame-based RDF/OWL KGs and those derived from LLMs. This endeavour is crucial to enhance our understanding of the capabilities and limitations of LLMs and to identify to which aspects we could bring the most value with a hybrid KE framework at the crossroads of NLP/NLU and SW.

2.6. Software and Data Release

We collect in this subsection the main software and data resources mentioned in Section 2 of this deliverable. Details about their compliance with the FAIR protocol is reported in Chapter 5 of this report.

- Polifonia Knowledge Extractor - Available at <https://github.com/polifonia-project/Polifonia-Knowledge-Extractor>
- AMR2FRED - Available at <https://github.com/polifonia-project/amr2Fred>
- Text2AMR2FRED API - Available at: <http://framester.istc.cnr.it/txt-amr-fred/api/docs/>
- Text2AMR2FRED WebApp - Available at: <https://arco.istc.cnr.it/txt-amr-fred/>
- Machine Reading suite - Available at: <https://github.com/polifonia-project/machine-reading>
- MusicBO Knowledge Graph - Available at: <https://github.com/polifonia-project/musicbo-knowledge-graph>
- MusicBO Knowledge Graph SPARQL endpoint - Available at: <https://polifonia.disi.unibo.it/musicbo/sparql>;
- MusicBO Knowledge Graph MELODY data story - Available at: https://projects.dharc.unibo.it/melody/musicbo/music_in_bologna_knowledge_graph_overview.
- AMR evaluation web tool - Available at: <http://framester.istc.cnr.it/amr-eval>.
- Comparison with Large Language Models - Proof-of-Concept Study - Available at: <https://github.com/polifonia-project/llms-vs-specialised-knowledge>.

3. OCR post-correction

3.1. Introduction

Optical Character Recognition (OCR) is the process by which graphemes in images can be identified and converted into machine-encoded text. OCR has a long history that dates back to the 1970s when the first computer programs capable of recognizing text written in different fonts was introduced [42]. Nowadays, it continues to be a prolific research area with several applications in the industrial sector [43].

OCR involves two fundamental steps, namely: i) image pre-processing; and ii) text recognition. In the first step, images are segmented in order to identify textual sections, textual lines and single characters areas. In the second step, image segments are analyzed in order to capture visual patterns that can be used to produce a ranked list of candidate characters. An additional step in the OCR pipeline, called post-OCR correction¹ (POC henceforth), is required to overcome some limitations of character identification that cause the prediction of incorrect sequences. These errors are characterized by the production of non-words, nonsensical text or ungrammatical sentences and are particularly frequent in case of historical documents. In fact, this type of documents have peculiarities that are difficult to manage by an OCR engine without a dedicated training set.

POC allows to substantially decrease the error rate of an OCR engine alleviating the production of ungrammatical/nonsensical sequences that arise especially when the prediction of characters in an OCR engine is not conditioned on linguistic information and the characters are produced independently, one after another. This information can be provided at word level to identify non-words by using a pre-defined vocabulary, and providing a set of replacements for non-words, e.g. *paft* → *past* or *path*. POC techniques can work also at phrase level, giving the possibility to propose replacements that are more likely to appear in a determined context than others, according to a Pre-trained Language Model (PLM).

In this work, we use a PLM to supply this information, allowing the identification of incorrect sequences and the selection of context-dependent replacements. Specifically, we will use the *emphseq2seq* paradigm [44] in which a string of text with potential OCR errors is given as input to an encoder that produces a latent representation of the sequence. This representation is then elaborated by a decoder that in turn produces as output another string of text possibly correcting the OCR errors. As we will see later, this class of models can work also in reverse, i.e., from error free sequences to sequences with errors.

The use of PLMs trained with a denoising objective, such as BART [45] and T5 [46] has been demonstrated to be effective for many NLP tasks [47]. It is particularly suited also for POC. In fact, PLMs are trained on a task very similar to POC, based on the reconstruction of artificially corrupted strings. However, PLMs alone are not sufficient because they are trained on specific data, mainly web documents [48], while POC involves heterogeneous situations determined by the language of the documents, the publication year, the type of documents, the OCR engine used and the style peculiar to a determined document type, just to name a few. Hence, PLMs need to be adapted through fine-tuning and transfer learning [49] to perform POC. Furthermore, the training data for this task are relatively scarce [50]; POC benchmarks have been generated from a specific set of documents and created by OCR engines that have been tuned to work on a specific setting [50]. Given the variability of the task that involves arbitrarily different documents, such scenario may lead to generalization problems.

To overcome these problems, we propose DENOISE a new technique that enables the consistency training of Transformer-based POC models. It is based on data augmentation and allows to mitigate an intrinsic problem of POC models: the domain adaptation. DENOISE allows to produce training data for arbitrary situations, making it possible to train new models specifically tailored to work on a very specific setting, adapting to different document formats, fonts and languages. This alleviates the cost of annotating new training sets by automatically generating

¹In the literature this task is also called OCR post-processing, OCR post-correction or OCR post-hoc correction.

a corruption of clean textual document similar to that produced by a OCR engine. Furthermore, our Transformer-based approach to POC has the advantage to inherently work at character and at word level overcoming the sparsity problems that affects POC models that work at word-level only [51].

The contribution of this work can be summarized in the following points:

- A new set of state-of-the-art models that can work on different languages and on different historical periods;
- Two methodologies to create silver training data for the task of POC;
- Silver datasets to train POC models;

3.2. Background and State of the Art

The literature on POC is broad and diversified, for this reason we divided it in the three main categories focusing on methodologies that can be directly compared to our approach and including also data augmentation techniques. For a detailed review on POC we refer to [52].

Generative approaches The first approaches to POC were based on generative probabilistic methods at word [53] and at character level [54]. These methods employ the noisy channel framework to formulate the correction problem. The former needs a predefined lexicon to determine acceptable words, the latter, working at character level, disposes of this requirement and can be applied without restriction also to low density languages for which lexical resources are scarce.

Multi-input approaches Multi-input approaches to POC analyze different output produced by the same OCR engine with different settings or by different engines. The idea behind these approaches is that different OCR views may make different mistakes and for this reason a reconciliation of these views that takes only the best parts of them, may produce a more accurate output. The models based on this paradigm use ensemble methods and majority voting schemas [55, 56, 57, 58, 59]. A method based on pre-trained generative language models is proposed in [60]. The first step of this approaches consists in identifying differences among sequences, the second step consists in calculating what is the more probable continuation of the sequences at the divergence point. For this computation, instead of using voting schemas, as is customary for this kind of approaches [61, 62, 63], a PLM (i.e., GPT3 [64]) was used to compute perplexity and selecting the continuation with the lowest score.

Sequence-to-sequence approaches Statistical and neural machine translation models were used extensively in POC [51, 65], even if notoriously machine translation requires more training data than that available for POC [66]. However, the idea behind this line of research is to cast POC as a machine translation task, in which the text produced by an OCR engine has to be translated into its correct form. AN example of this approach has been proposed in [67] where an SMT system has been successfully trained to translate historical French texts with OCR errors into corrected text. In [51] it is provided an extensive analysis of statistical and neural machine translation models for character-based POC, reporting that character-based machine translation techniques can be used for POC and that SMT systems perform better in error correction, while NMT systems achieve higher results in error detection. A two-step approach based on recurrent neural networks (RNN) has been proposed in [68]. The first step serves to detect strings with OCR errors, the second one feeds these strings into a Long Short Term Memory (LSTM) architecture for the *seq2seq* translation step. [69] proposed an character level encoder-decoder model that encodes the input through a combination of RNN and deep ConvNet [70] networks. The idea behind this approach is that RNNs capture the global input context and ConvNets construct local sub-word structures. The errors are corrected at decoding time in which the decoder through an attention mechanism on the input produces the corrected text. [71] proposed a *seq2seq* Transformer-based approach to process long sequences and used as case in point POC. The strategy that they proposed involves the splitting of the input document in character n-grams and combining their individual corrections into the final output using an ensemble of a large number of sequence models. The need

of having efficient tools for the digitization of documents in low-resourced languages was emphasized by [72] that recently proposed a semi-supervised models based on self-training to enable the use of an OCR engine trained on high-resourced languages also on low-resourced languages exploiting script similarities and using POC techniques to correct errors.

3.2.1. Data Augmentation

Data Augmentation (DA) consists in increasing training data quantity and diversity without directly collecting and annotating more data. Current strategies dwells in adding slightly modified copies of existing data or creating synthetic data with desired features [73]. The aim of DA is to reduce overfitting or underfitting in machine learning models, acting as a regularizer [73]. DA approaches in NLP are based primarily on lexical substitution [74] techniques, that involves the replacements of some words in a sentence without altering its overall meaning [75, 76]. Approaches based on the creation of new samples are limited to the generation of new instances for classification tasks. Approaches of this kind have been proposed by [77] and [78] that fine-tuned GPT-2 to generate sentences that belong to a predefined class. To the best of our knowledge, ours is the first generative approach that produces new samples for *seq2seq* tasks without modifying examples from a gold training set like the popular *back-translation* approach proposed by [34].

DA techniques for POC are mainly based on edit distance modifications and on static word embedding models. [79] created training data comparing selected words from a clean sentence with the most similar words in a word embedding model, i.e., Word2Vec model [80], trained on noisy data, assuming that OCR errors for the same target word are sporadic and for this reason noisy words will have similar representations to their respective target. Noisy words are then filtered in order to avoid to detect false positive and then replaced in the string. [81] create training data by clustering repeated texts in a corpus. For each cluster they group similar words based on Levenshtain distance. Each word group is then aligned and the most common character for each position is chosen as candidate for the replacements in a clean string.

Figure 3.1: A schematic representation of DENOISE. (1a) Gold POC dataset are collected, inverted and fed into a *seq2seq* model that corrupts strings. (1b) noisy texts are collected to train a noisy word2vec model, another word2vec model is also trained with clean data. (2a) CORRUPTER is used to create silver datasets for POC. (2b) Clean sentences are collected and then corrupted and filtered using two word2vec models trained in 1.b. Input and output are merged to create a silver dataset for POC. (3) Gold and silver data are fed to a *seq2seq* model to train PURIFIER.

3.3. Method

POC can be defined as the task of translating a sequence of n tokens $\hat{S} = \hat{s}_1, \hat{s}_2, \dots, \hat{s}_n$, produced by an OCR engine, into a new sequence $S = s_1, s_2, \dots, s_m$, that corresponds to the sequence of tokens printed in the original

document. Due to segmentation errors that may arise during the OCR process, the length of the two sequences is not necessarily the same. Usually, the task can be divided into two sub-tasks: i) error detection; and ii) error correction. The first sub-task deals with the identification of possible error in the OCR string and then passes this information to the error correction model that for each detected error produces a set of possible corrections. However, POC is conducted end-to-end by modern *seq2seq* models, able to produce S directly from \hat{S} , in this case error detection is not required but performed implicitly.

Our approach to POC can be divided into three main components, as described in Figure 3.1. The first component is used to train CORRUPTER a model, $C_{\Theta}(\hat{s}|s)$, based on *seq2seq* modeling or static word embedding, that takes as input a clean string, s , and generates its corrupted version \hat{s} . The second component is AMPLIFIER, that uses CORRUPTER to create silver datasets for POC. The third component produces training schedules to using gold and/or silver data to train PURIFIER, a *seq2seq* model, $P_{\Theta}(s|\hat{s})$, that takes as input a possibly corrupted string \hat{s} and generates its corrected version s .

3.3.1. Sequence-to-Sequence Modeling

In this work we use *seq2seq* modeling for both the noisification of text, used for data augmentation and the denoisification of text used to correct OCR errors. Given an input sequence \hat{S} , the model has to learn to generate the correct text S . This formulation can be formally seen as a conditional generation problem in which the probability $P(\mathbf{S}|\hat{\mathbf{S}})$ of generating the tokenization $\mathbf{S} = \langle s_1, s_2, \dots, s_i, \dots, s_{|\mathbf{S}|} \rangle$ of the transcribed text is conditioned on the tokenization $\hat{\mathbf{S}} = \langle \hat{s}_1, \hat{s}_2, \dots, \hat{s}_{|\hat{\mathbf{S}}|} \rangle$ of the input text. That is:

$$P(\mathbf{S}|\hat{\mathbf{S}}) = \prod_{i=2}^{|\mathbf{S}|} P(s_i | \mathbf{s}_{1:i-1}, \hat{\mathbf{S}}) \quad (3.1)$$

where s_i is the i -th element of the generated output sequence \mathbf{S} and $\mathbf{s}_{1:i-1} = \langle s_1, s_2, \dots, s_{i-1} \rangle$. Therefore, the probability $P(\mathbf{S}|\hat{\mathbf{S}})$ of the tokenization \mathbf{S} for the given sentence $\hat{\mathbf{S}}$ is computed as the product of the probability of generating each token s_i of \mathbf{S} in an autoregressive fashion. The same formulation of the problem, but with inverted variables, i.e., $P(\hat{\mathbf{S}}|\mathbf{S})$, can be used to train a noisifier that takes as input clean text and learns to generate incorrect versions of it.

3.3.2. CORRUPTER

The first step of our pipeline consists in training a text noisifier. To this end we have two options: training a *seq2seq* model (see Figure 3.1 (1a)) that takes as input clean text and produces noisy text; and using static word embedding models trained on noisy text to replace random words in clean sentences (see Figure 3.1 (1b)).

The steps necessary to develop the first noisifier are: i) collect gold training sets; ii) preprocess them to make string pairs fit in our architecture; iii) invert input and output, i.e., from *noisy text* \rightarrow *clean text*, to *clean text* \rightarrow *noisy text*; iv) train a *seq2seq* model to learn to generate $P(\hat{\mathbf{S}}|\mathbf{S})$. We called this methodology CORRUPTER. Instead of training our models from scratch, we initialized their weights with the ones from a pre-trained language model. This is beneficial for two reasons: i) the PLMs used are trained to denoise artificially-corrupted sentences, they already have learnt to solve a task similar to POC. ii) these PLMs have already learnt a language model that can be used efficiently to predict the next token in a sequence. However, the datasets used to train BART and mBART are composed of contemporary texts including books, stories, news, web content and Wikipedia articles, and thus deviating from the historical nature of documents that are under study in this work. Specific training data are thus necessary for language and style adaptation.

An alternative noisifier can be developed following these steps (see Figure 3.1 (1b)): i) select relevant clean texts for the task, ii) train a word2vec model on noisy text (noisy_w2v), possibly relevant for the specific task, iii) train a word2vec model on clean texts (clean_word2vec), iv) select words randomly from the clean sentences, v) for each of these words collect the most similar words in noisy_word2vec, vi) check if these similar words are also the most

similar in `clean_w2v` for the same word, vii) if no, replace the random word in the sentence with its most similar, viii) use the modified sentences paired with the original sentence to create an silver training set for a POC model. This approach doesn't guarantee to obtain grammatical sentences and it is expected to produce non-contextualized OCR errors.

3.3.3. AMPLIFIER

The second step of our pipeline deals with the data augmentation. We developed two approaches for this subtask: i.e, generative augmentation and word2vec augmentation.

Generative augmentation. The steps involved for this process are (see Figure 3.1 (2a)): i) collecting clean sentences that can be useful to the resolution of a particular POC case; ii) giving these sentences as input to `CORRUPTER` to obtain corresponding sentences with OCR errors; iii) measure the error rate in each sentence pair in order to filter pairs with an error rate higher than a given threshold (high error rates could be the signal of wrong productions or hallucination in conditional language generation [82]); iv) arrange the filtered sentence pairs in the same way POC datasets are constructed.

Word2vec augmentation. The steps involved for this process are similar to the ones described above and consist in (see Figure 3.1 (2b)): i) train a word2vec model (`clean_w2v`) using only clean documents; ii) train a word2vec model (`noisy_w2v`) using noisy OCRed documents; iii) collecting clean sentences that can be useful to the resolution of a particular POC case; iv) select target words randomly from these sentences; v) use `noisy_w2v` to find the most similar word to the randomly selected targets; vi) if the similar word is not among top 10 most similar words in `clean_w2v` the target word is replaced with the its (possibly noisy) most similar one;

3.3.4. PURIFIER

The last step of our framework consist in training a seq2seq model to correct OCR errors. `PURIFIER` has the same training used for `CORRUPTER`, it can use both gold data and silver data, generated with `AMPLIFIER`. It can be based on a monolingual or a multilingual language model to allow multi-lingual transfer [83].

3.3.5. Implementation Details

Pre-processing The output of an OCR engine is usually a string that correspond to the transcription of lines of text in a printed document. However, in the benchmarks that we are using the line end information is missing and the output of all the lines of a document are merged. This can result in very long strings that pose serious computational problems, even for the computation of the Levenshtain distance [84], since the documents can have more that 50,000 characters. For this reason we decided to split the documents and to create more tractable examples pairs. To achieve this goal we separated the documents texts into shorter strings, devising a very simple heuristic. Given two aligned document strings i and g we separated them if a full stop is encountered in the sequence of characters of the g document, the length of the split string is higher than 20 characters and the character before the full stop is not a capital letter. The document strings \hat{i} and \hat{g} are dived into two sequences of aligned string pairs $I = [i_1, i_2, \dots, i_n]$ and $G = [g_1, g_2, \dots, g_n]$ where for each i_j there is an aligned string g_j . However, even if we are using gold datasets, it is possible that in some cases the alignment is not correct. Hence, to avoid to work with unaligned pairs we decided to discard all the string pairs that have a Character Error Rate (CER) (see Section 3.4.1) higher than 0.6. This value was selected manually checking the alignment on a sample of 1,000 pairs. Once the pairs are filtered, all the characters inserted by the developer of the datasets for the character level alignment of the documents are removed. We also replaced non-ASCII characters from the strings using a mapping to ASCII characters. This operation was necessary for two reasons: i) to preserve the vocabulary of the pre-trained models used in this work; ii) to deal with intrinsic errors of the OCR engine that can be solved without sophisticated methods, e.g., the production of Cyrillic characters instead of Latin ones, such as K instead of K .

PLMs The PLMs used in this work are BART and mBART. They have 12 stacked Transformer layers for the encoder and the decoder with model dimension of 1024 on 16 heads ($\sim 680\text{M}$ parameters). The main difference between these two models relies on the training data. BART was trained to denoise English texts, while mBART was trained on texts in 50 languages, requiring a much larger vocabulary (50,265 vs. 250,000).

Clean sentences The clean sentences used by AMPLIFIER have been obtained sampling randomly from two data sources: the Gutenberg Project dataset [85] for what concerns the English language and OSCAR (Open Super-large Crawled Aggregated coRpus) [48] for all the other languages.

Word2vec models We used Wikipedia to train `clean_w2v` and the Polifonia Corpus to train `noisy_w2v`. Both models use the skip-gram architecture and have a vector size of 200 dimensions. The window size of these models was set to 5, the minimum number word occurrences was set to 0 in order to capture also phenomena that occur rarely, and the number of negative samples was set to 5.

3.4. Experimental Setup

We conducted an extensive evaluation to test the performances of `DENOISE` with different configurations. The main objective of this evaluation is to see how performances change with the variation of the underline PLM and the variation of the training schedule. In the following paragraphs of this Section we will describe the metrics used for the evaluation, the benchmarks, the models and the training schedules.

3.4.1. Metrics

Character Error Rate Character Error Rate (CER) is defined as the minimum number of operations required to transform a string into another, i.e., the string predicted by a model and the corresponding string for the same example in a ground truth. It is computed summing the number of substitutions (S), the number of deletions (D) and the number of insertions (I) and dividing it by the number of characters in a string (N), as in the following equation:

$$CER = \frac{S + D + I}{N} \quad (3.2)$$

Word Error Rate Word Error Rate (WER) is similar to CER but instead of considering differences between characters, it operates at word level, calculating the minimum number of word substitutions, deletions and insertions necessary to transform the input string into a target string. It is computed as:

$$WER = \frac{S_w + D_w + I_w}{N_w} \quad (3.3)$$

Relative Improvement Another metric commonly used on POC is Relative Improvement (RelImp). It allows to quantify the reduction of CER of a given model and is computed as:

$$RelImp = 100 * \left(1 - \frac{CER_{pred}}{CER_{imp}} \right) \quad (3.4)$$

Table 3.1: Statistics of the datasets used for the evaluation.

dataset	lang	split	#items	#words	μ CER	σ CER	μ WER	σ WER
GHT _{high}	EN	train	73654	4120950	0.07	0.07	0.15	0.11
GHT _{high}	EN	dev	9189	512985	0.07	0.07	0.15	0.11
GHT _{high}	EN	test	9255	514495	0.07	0.07	0.15	0.11
GHT _{low}	EN	train	39782	2234299	0.06	0.06	0.13	0.1
GHT _{low}	EN	dev	4922	274304	0.06	0.06	0.13	0.1
GHT _{low}	EN	test	4917	274556	0.06	0.06	0.13	0.1
ICDAR2019	DE	dev	7148	377689	0.23	0.09	0.77	0.17
ICDAR2019	DE	test	15258	923494	0.24	0.09	0.76	0.22
ICDAR2019	DE	train	40510	2441899	0.24	0.1	0.74	0.2
ICDAR2019	FR	dev	2509	70752	0.07	0.12	0.19	0.21
ICDAR2019	FR	test	4296	290160	0.08	0.14	0.22	0.22
ICDAR2019	FR	train	14218	1084265	0.07	0.11	0.22	0.22
ICDAR2017 _{mono}	EN	dev	2762	149670	0.08	0.08	0.24	0.16
ICDAR2017 _{mono}	EN	test	3316	275874	0.04	0.06	0.15	0.19
ICDAR2017 _{mono}	EN	train	15657	1100996	0.05	0.09	0.13	0.16
ICDAR2017 _{per}	EN	dev	1297	71933	0.09	0.11	0.22	0.18
ICDAR2017 _{per}	EN	test	2481	122002	0.1	0.13	0.23	0.22
ICDAR2017 _{per}	EN	train	7354	441563	0.09	0.12	0.21	0.2
ICDAR2017 _{mono}	FR	dev	3334	166686	0.02	0.04	0.09	0.12
ICDAR2017 _{mono}	FR	test	2547	124782	0.02	0.04	0.09	0.12
ICDAR2017 _{mono}	FR	train	18893	1031749	0.02	0.04	0.1	0.14
ICDAR2017 _{per}	FR	dev	1874	80326	0.06	0.12	0.12	0.16
ICDAR2017 _{per}	FR	test	4272	205639	0.04	0.08	0.14	0.18
ICDAR2017 _{per}	FR	train	10622	424017	0.07	0.11	0.2	0.21

3.4.2. Gold Datasets

To evaluate the performance DENOISE, we used 8 datasets that are part of 2 standard POC benchmarks (ICDAR2019 and ICDAR2017) and a recently released one (Gutenberg-HathiTrust Parallel Corpus, GHT). The selected datasets cover three languages i.e. English, French and German; have texts from different sources, including monographs, periodicals and receipts; and contain different levels of errors, ranging from 0.24 to 0.02 CER.

We selected these three datasets for different reasons: i) it is easy to compare our results with other state-of-the-art models; ii) the documents are from different sources, i.e. periodicals and monographs; iii) they cover 10 languages, i.e. Bulgarian, Czech, Dutch, English, Finish, French, German, Polish, Spanish and Slovak, allowing to extend our analysis; iv) the extracted texts have been obtained using commercial and open-source OCR engines; v) they contain documents published on a large time frame, i.e. 1654-2000. vi) they contain texts from different domains, including medicine, history, agriculture, finance and fiction.

The main features of these datasets are presented in Table 3.1 and a short description is provided below.

ICDAR2017 ICDAR2017² [86] was released as a competition dataset within the International Conference on Document Analysis and Recognition (ICDAR) in 2017. The challenge was organized as two independent tasks: i) error detection and, ii) error correction. This benchmark consists of 12M OCR-ed symbols along with an aligned ground truth. It divided by language (English and French) and by document type (monographs and periodicals). All four resulting datasets have been used in our evaluation.

²<https://sites.google.com/view/icdar2017-postcorrectionocr/dataset>

ICDAR2019 ICDAR2019³ [87] was released as a competition dataset within ICDAR 2019. It contains approximately 22M symbols and covers 10 European languages: Bulgarian, Czech, Dutch, English, Finnish, French, German, Polish, Spanish and Slovak. In our evaluation we used the datasets in French and in German⁴.

Gutenberg-HathiTrust Parallel Corpus Gutenberg-HathiTrust Parallel Corpus⁵ [88] is a large-scale dataset for English POC. It contains aligned pairs of uncorrected OCR-impacted and human-proofread books in six domains published from 1780 to 1993. The clean data have been collected from Gutenberg Project and consist of human-proofread texts. Uncorrected OCR texts have been selected from the HathiTrust Digital Library and paired with texts in Gutenberg Project. There are two versions of this dataset, one contains sentence pairs with low CER and another one contains sentence pairs with high CER. We used both datasets for our evaluation even though we found that many sentence pairs in these collections do not contain real errors, but only variants of the same sentence that differ not for errors but for different punctuation (e.g.: a comma instead of a semicolon or a single quote instead of a double quote).

3.4.3. Silver Datasets

Generative augmentation To train our generative noisifier, i.e. CORRUPTER, we used a monolingual language model for English (BART-large) and a multilingual one (mBART-large-50). To train the monolingual CORRUPTER, we used all the English training sets described in Table 3.1, limiting larger training sets to 10,000 pairs, in order not to bias the model towards a specific dataset. To train the multilingual CORRUPTER we followed the same procedure, but this time we used training sets also in French and German. The development sets were constructed in the same way for model selection over 5 epochs. The trained models were then used to noisify 20,000 sentence pairs that were then inverted and used to train a PURIFIER.

W2v augmentation The datasets created with the w2v method have the same size of the datasets created with the generative CORRUPTER.

3.4.4. Models and training schedules

The PLM used in this work are BART (base and large) [45] for the English language or mBART [89] for all languages. BART-base has ~140 M parameters, BART-large has ~400 M parameters and mBART ~610 M. BART was trained only on monolingual data while mBART was trained on data in 50 languages that include all the languages used in our evaluation, namely English, French and German. To test the different components of DENOISE we trained it with different training schedules, namely: *zero-shot* (0-shot); using only the training data of each dataset (original); using only data augmentation created with AMPLIFIER (aug gen) or word2vec (aug w2v); and combining gold and silver data (aug gen/w2v + original). All models have been trained for 10 epochs selecting the model with the best performances on the development set of each dataset.

3.5. Results and Analysis

In this Section, the results of our experiments on each dataset are presented and discussed.

³<https://sites.google.com/view/icdar2019-postcorrectionocr/dataset>

⁴We discarded the ICDAR2019 English dataset because we found alignment problems and because it is very small

⁵<https://databank.illinois.edu/datasets/IDB-1685085>

Table 3.2: Results on GHT_{high} - EN.

model	training	CER ↓	WER ↓	Rel.Imp. CER ↑	Rel.Imp. WER ↑
dataset		0.7	0.15		
BART-base	0-shot	0.09	0.18	-28.57	-20.00
BART-base	original	0.05	0.10	28.57	33.33
BART-base	aug gen	0.06	0.14	14.29	6.67
BART-base	aug w2v	0.06	0.14	14.29	6.67
BART-large	0-shot	0.11	0.20	-57.14	-33.33
BART-large	original	0.05	0.10	28.57	33.33
BART-large	aug gen	0.06	0.14	14.29	6.67
BART-large	aug w2v	0.06	0.14	14.29	6.67
mBART	0-shot	0.08	0.22	-14.29	-46.67
mBART	original	0.05	0.10	28.57	33.33
mBART	aug gen	0.06	0.14	14.29	6.67
mBART	aug w2v	0.06	0.14	14.29	6.67

3.5.1. Gutenberg-HathiTrust - High - EN

The evaluation on Gutenberg-HathiTrust High is presented in Table 3.2. The first point to notice is that, as we have hypothesized at the beginning of this work, language models alone are not sufficient to deal with the task. In fact, the performances of the zero shot models are always negative in term of relative improvement. Training the models with the original data of the dataset is beneficial allowing to gain around 30% CER and WER improvements. Also the use of silver training data is beneficial allowing to achieve results similar to those of the models trained with gold data. Another interesting trend is represented by the fact that the results have no variation changing the underlying language model or the data augmentation technique.

Table 3.3: Results on GHT_{low} - EN.

model	training	CER ↓	WER ↓	Rel.Imp. CER ↑	Rel.Imp. WER ↑
dataset		0.6	0.13		
BART-base	0-shot	0.06	0.15	0.00	-15.38
BART-base	original	0.05	0.11	16.67	15.38
BART-base	aug gen	0.05	0.11	16.67	15.38
BART-base	aug w2v	0.05	0.11	16.67	15.38
BART-large	0-shot	0.09	0.16	-50.00	-23.08
BART-large	original	0.05	0.11	16.67	15.38
BART-large	aug gen	0.05	0.11	16.67	15.38
BART-large	aug w2v	0.05	0.11	16.67	15.38
mBART	0-shot	0.08	0.20	-33.33	-53.85
mBART	original	0.05	0.11	16.67	15.38
mBART	aug gen	0.05	0.11	16.67	15.38
mBART	aug w2v	0.05	0.11	16.67	15.38

3.5.2. Gutenberg-HathiTrust - Low - EN

The evaluation on Gutenberg-HathiTrust Low is presented in Table 3.2. The results are very similar to those already discussed for GHT_{high} the only different is that in this case BART-base in *zero-shot* produces the same CER of the dataset. This is probably due to the fact that the sentence pairs in this dataset have no big differences and for this reason the model does not modify the input.

Table 3.4: Results on ICDAR2019 - DE.

model	training	CER ↓	WER ↓	Rel.Imp.	CER ↑	Rel.Imp.	WER ↑
dataset	-	0.24	0.76		-		-
mBART	0-shot	0.79	0.78		-229.17		-169
mBART	original	0.13	0.37		45.8		51.3
mBART	aug gen	0.16	0.42		33.3		44.7
mBART	aug w2v	0.19	0.45		20.8		40.8

3.5.3. ICDAR2019 - DE

The evaluation on the German part of the ICDAR2019 dataset is conducted only on mBART. The first factor to notice is the high error rate that characterize this dataset compared to the previous ones. This makes the correction of the dataset very challenging. In fact, as we can see from Table 3.4 the performance of the *zero-shot* model are very poor. Investigating the text generated by this model we noticed that it tends to continue the sentences given as input impacting negatively the calculation of CER and WER. On the contrary, the results obtained training the mBART with the original data of this benchmark are remarkable, achieving a relative improvements of 45.8 and 51.3% in CER and WER respectively. These big improvements are probably due to the size of the dataset that with 2.5M words is among the largest of our evaluation. This training set has also a nice effect on the training of PURIFIER that allows to generate good quality silver data (aug gen), given the performances similar to those of the same model trained with gold data. The improvements of the w2v noisifier are slightly lower, nevertheless they are still positive.

Table 3.5: Results on ICDAR2019 - FR.

model	training	CER ↓	WER ↓	Rel.Imp.	CER ↑	Rel.Imp.	WER ↑
dataset	-	0.08	0.14		-		-
mBART	0-shot	1.96	0.30		-2350		-114
mBART	original	0.09	0.15		-12.5		-7
mBART	aug gen	0.10	0.16		-25		-14
mBART	aug w2v	0.10	0.17		-25		-21

3.5.4. ICDAR2019 - FR

The first observation that emerges from the analysis of the results of this dataset is the high error rates of the zero-shot model. Inspecting the results, we noticed that the model hallucinate easily because the input of this dataset is often composed by numbers and lists of items from receipts. This kind of input, probably unusual for the model, produces the insertion of new items and digits in the text that result in heavily altering the original text. Another observation that we can make is that all the tested models are not able to improve the quality of text in these kind of documents, simply because it could be arbitrary to change a 9 with an 8 in a large number.

3.5.5. ICDAR2017 - EN - monograph

The models tested on this dataset struggle to improve the quality the texts. Inspecting the results, we noticed that in many cases they are not able to correct page segmentation errors and that in several cases the models are not able delete sequences of nonsensical characters, produced by the OCR engine interpreting as text non-textual parts of the page. For this kind of errors, we argue that there are not enough training instances and for this reason the models are not able to deal with them. This is also demonstrated by the models trained with silver data. In fact, these datasets do not contain this kind of errors.

Table 3.6: Results on ICDAR2017_{mono} - EN.

model	training	CER ↓	WER ↓	Rel.Imp. CER ↑	Rel.Imp. WER ↑
dataset	-	0.04	0.06	-	-
BART-base	0-shot	0.19	0.18	-375	-200
BART-base	original	0.04	0.11	0	-83
BART-base	aug gen	0.05	0.12	-25	-100
BART-base	aug w2v	0.06	0.14	-50	-133
BART-large	0-shot	0.21	0.23	-425	-283
BART-large	original	0.05	0.12	-25	-100
BART-large	aug gen	0.05	0.12	-25	-100
BART-large	aug w2v	0.06	0.14	-50	-133
mBART	0-shot	0.21	0.23	-425	-283
mBART	original	0.05	0.12	-25	-100
mBART	aug gen	0.05	0.12	-25	-100
mBART	aug w2v	0.06	0.14	-50	-133

Table 3.7: Results on ICDAR2017_{per} - EN.

model	training	CER ↓	WER ↓	Rel.Imp. CER ↑	Rel.Imp. WER ↑
dataset	-	0.10	0.13	-	-
BART-base	0-shot	0.20	0.29	-100	-123
BART-base	original	0.10	0.14	0	-8
BART-base	aug gen	0.15	0.17	-50	-31
BART-base	aug w2v	0.16	0.19	-60	-46
BART-large	0-shot	0.20	0.29	-100	-123
BART-large	original	0.11	0.14	-10	-8
BART-large	aug gen	0.15	0.17	-50	-31
BART-large	aug w2v	0.16	0.19	-60	-46
mBART	0-shot	0.20	0.29	-100	-123
mBART	original	0.11	0.14	-10	-8
mBART	aug gen	0.16	0.19	-60	-46
mBART	aug w2v	0.17	0.20	-70	-54

3.5.6. ICDAR2017 - EN - periodical

The models tested on this dataset are not able to decrease errors rates. The main reason for this behaviour is the size of the training set that is relatively small for sequence-to-sequence models. Inspecting the text generated by the models, we noticed that they are not able to correct page segmentation errors. This kind of errors are not directly imputable to an OCR but to layout identification, a step that is performed before the OCR. In this case, two textual columns in a document are interpreted as a single column and results in merging two lines of text that not necessarily contain errors. However the task, as it is implemented in this dataset, consist in deleting the text belonging to one of the two columns. From an inspection of the results, we observed that the models are not able to perform this action, just because there could be no OCR errors in the string and because to some extent it is arbitrary to decide which of the two parts of the merged line should be removed. We believe that this kind of task could be solved easily with a dedicated component that preprocesses the text.

3.5.7. ICDAR2017 - FR - monograph

The models and training schedules used on this dataset are not able to decrease its error rates. This is probably due to the fact that the training sets of are not large enough to allow the model to generalize. Furthermore, the inspecting the textual pairs, many errors are related to numbers as the dataset contains also OCRed receipts and addresses, two kinds texts that are difficult to handle, because the errors in them are independent from the context, especially

Table 3.8: Results on ICDAR2017_{mono} - FR.

model	training	CER ↓	WER ↓	Rel.Imp.	CER ↑	Rel.Imp.	WER ↑
dataset	-	0.02	0.04		-		-
mBART	0-shot	0.09	0.13		-350		-160
mBART	original	0.02	0.05		0		-25
mBART	aug gen	0.02	0.05		0		-25
mBART	aug w2v	0.03	0.05		-50		-25

with respect to digits.

Table 3.9: Results on ICDAR2017_{per} - FR.

model	training	CER ↓	WER ↓	Rel.Imp.	CER ↑	Rel.Imp.	WER ↑
dataset	-	0.04	0.08		-		-
mBART	0-shot	0.09	0.19		-125		-111
mBART	original	0.05	0.12		-25		-50
mBART	aug gen	0.05	0.13		-25		-63
mBART	aug w2v	0.06	0.14		-50		-75

3.5.8. ICDAR2017 - FR - periodical

The considerations made for ICDAR2017 - FR - monograph, can be extended also to this datasets. In fact, the tested models are not able to decrease error rates.

3.6. Conclusion

In this section we proposed a new set of tools for POC including: models for correcting OCRed documents in different languages; methodologies for creating training data for the task; and an extensive evaluation on generative approaches to POC. The evaluation allowed us to confirm that this task is very challenging and that the results of a model vary across benchmarks. The first observation that we can make is that the size of the underlying language model does not have a noticeable impact on the results, using BART-base, BART-large or even mBART does not have any impact on the considered datasets. Another observation that emerges clearly from the results is that the performances of the models are mainly influenced by the size of the gold training data and the level and kind of errors in them. Datasets with large training sets (ICDAR2019 DE, GHT_{high}) allow to achieve big improvements up to 45.8 Rel. Imp. CER. To the contrary, on datasets with small training sets and low error rates (ICDAR2017_{per} - FR, ICDAR2017_{mono} - FR) the models are not able to improve quality of the texts. In addition to this, datasets with typology of errors underrepresented in the training set, such as page segmentation, nonsensical sequences, are difficult to correct. Datasets with high error rates (ICDAR2019 DE) are also the ones higher improvements, indicating that the models learn easily to correct very noisy data but struggle to correct datasets in which only a small amount of error is present. This can be also due to the fact that in some cases, especially in the GHT datasets, the sentence pairs diverge only on punctuation. A closer look at these datasets demonstrated, in fact, that in many cases it is not possible to asses if a sentence pair contains OCR errors or it just represent two stylistically different versions of the same sentence.

With the experiments in this section, we were able to test to what extent the generation of silver data for POC is effective. We provided two procedures that have consistent results. However, we believe that these procedures can be improved. In particular, as future work we want to cover also other specific OCR problems, such as page segmentation and the production nonsensical sequences that arises when non-textual parts of the page are parsed

by the OCR engine. Another improvement that we want to develop consists in finding new ways to define the optimal quantity and diversification of silver data, in order to adapt to a specific set of documents. In deliverable 4.7, in fact, we aim at evaluating our knowledge extraction pipeline using the models proposed in this section to correct OCR errors, providing in this way an *in vivo* evaluation also for POC.

3.7. Software and Data Release

We collect in this subsection the main software and data resources of tools for POC mentioned in Section 3 of this deliverable. Details about their compliance with the FAIR protocol is reported in Chapter 5 of this report.

- Software and data resources of tools for POC mentioned in Section 3 - Available at <https://github.com/polifonia-project/generative-post-ocr-correction>.

4. Historical Entity Linking

4.1. Introduction

Named Entity Recognition and Classification (NERC) [12] and Entity Linking (EL), also referred to as Entity Disambiguation [90] are foundational tasks in knowledge extraction and have become progressively more relevant for historical documents due to the massive campaigns of digitisation carried out in recent years [91]. NERC consists of extracting mentions of named entities (such as people, locations, organisations, etc.) in text and assigning them to a pre-defined set of entity types, such as PERSON, LOCATION or ORGANISATION. Entity Linking (EL) consists of correlating named entities' mentions to the actual entity they refer to, choosing possible candidates from a reference Knowledge Base (KB), such as Wikipedia¹, DBPedia², Wikidata³. The information required to perform such a choice is commonly retrieved from the context in which the named entity occurs. As an example, the reader may consider the named entity's mention *Jordan*, as seen in the example sentences below:

Jordan joined the Bulls in 1984 as the third overall draft pick.

Sunni Islam is the dominant religion in Jordan.

It may refer to *Jordan*, the country in West Asia indexed in a particular English Wikipedia page and Wikidata item⁴, and to the basketball player *Michael Jordan*, indexed in another English Wikipedia page and Wikidata item⁵. Looking at the two sentences in the reported examples, the surrounding context of the mentions *Jordan* makes it clear which entity in the KB "Jordan" refers to, demonstrating context's importance in EL tasks.

As summarised in [91], NERC and EL are particularly challenging on historical documents due to the noisy quality of the plain text derived through Optical Character Recognition (OCR) technologies. Also, non-contemporary language differs from nowadays' varieties in diverse lexical, morpho-syntactic and semantic aspects, such as spelling variation, sentence structure and naming conventions. Furthermore, annotated datasets of historical texts are scarce, and state-of-the-art (SotA) models, based on the supervised paradigm, are trained on contemporary data based mainly on web documents [92, 93, 10]. The scarcity of resources decelerates progress in the most promising approaches to the tasks explored recently [94] and hinders the possibility of studying important cultural heritage documents with these tools. In addition, EL is especially challenging when applied to historical text, especially when it involves entity disambiguation (linking named entities whose superficial mention is common to many named entities to their correct entry in a knowledge base). The reader may take, for example, the named entity's mention *Naumann*, as seen in the example sentence below, extrapolated from the issue n. 22 of the music periodical *The Quarterly Musical Magazine And Review*, dating back to 1824, part of the PTC¹⁵:

The next is a solo for an alto, and a quartet from Naumann.

It may refer to ~30 different named entities, as the English Wikipedia disambiguation page reports⁶. As it can be inferred from the context provided by the sentence in the example below, the correct named entity to link should be a person related to music. Two of the listed person named entities are related to music:

*Johann Gottlieb Naumann (1741–1801), German composer*⁷;

*Ernst Naumann (1832–1910), German composer*⁸.

¹wikipedia.org

²<https://www.dbpedia.org/>

³wikidata.org

⁴<https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Jordan>; <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q810>

⁵https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Michael_Jordan; <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q41421>

⁶<https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Naumann>

⁷https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Johann_Gottlieb_Naumann; <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q213927>

⁸https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Ernst_Naumann; <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q5395101>

As it can be inferred by looking at the dates of birth of the two person named entities listed above, if cross-checked with the date of issue of the periodical in which Naumann occurs as a named entity mention, the correct entity to link is the first one.

Figure 4.1: AMR graph resulting from the text2AMR parsing powered by [15, SPRING] of the sentence "Fabio Constantini flourished about the year 1630, and ultimately became maestro at the chapel of Loretto.", extrapolated from *The Quarterly Musical Magazine And Review*, n. 22 (1824), part of the *Periodicals* module of the PTC¹⁵.

We hypothesise that the *popularity bias* in state-of-the-art (SotA) neural entity linkers, a phenomenon investigated by [10], intensifies when applied to entities extrapolated from historical texts. Popularity bias causes popular entities, i.e. entities that are more frequent in a training set, to be preferred to less frequent entities, even if the context in which they appear is unambiguous. The cause of this heightened bias can be traced back to historical entities being less represented in popular training datasets [95]. Furthermore, in the context of historical documents, this popularity bias tends to evolve into a peculiar bias, which we term as *temporal bias*. This is the tendency for these neural entity linkers to favour contemporary entities over historical entities, even if other unambiguous historical entities are mentioned in the same context. Eventually, they reach lower performance when applied to historical entities found in historical texts, as compared to the performance reached when applied to contemporary entities found in contemporary texts. For example, it is possible to appreciate this phenomenon in the AMR graph produced by the text2AMR step of our Text2AMR2FRED⁵⁴ (cfr. 2) tool, reported in Figure 4.1. In the AMR graph, the NEs recognition and classification (NERC) performed by [15, SPRING] correctly recognises the superficial named entity's mention *Fabio Constantini*, which is erroneously linked by [9, BLINK] to the Wikipedia page of *Claudio Constantini*⁹, a Peruvian composer born in 1983. The correct link should be to the Wikidata entity *Fabio Constantini*¹⁰, with QID Q3737659, an Italian composer born in 1575.

We aim to mitigate the need for gold-standard resources containing NERC- and EL-annotated historical documents by releasing a new model for historical entity linking and a new benchmark for the task. We release the Musical Heritage Historical named Entities Recognition, Classification and Linking benchmark (MHERCL v0.1) to enrich the landscape of gold-standard resources containing NERC- and EL-annotated historical documents, and ELD (Entity Linking Dynamics), an innovative model for Entity Linking that grounds its inner entity disambiguation process to the context in which entities appear, relying on relaxation labelling processes [96].

⁹https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Claudio_Constantini

¹⁰<https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q3737659>

The remainder of this section is organised as follows. In sub-section 4.2, we summarise the most relevant contributions regarding historical dataset collection and implemented models specifically trained on historical documents. In sub-section 4.3.1, we depict the background work that made the building of MHERCL v0.1 possible, and we describe the benchmark in terms of sampling, annotation guidelines, statistics and release details. In sub-section 4.4, we describe the implementation of ELD. We report our experiments' results in sub-section 4.5.

4.2. State-of-the-Art

4.2.1. Benchmarks

4.2.1.1. Historical

Recent surveys highlight how historical texts are rarely included in popular training datasets [95]. In recent years, HIPE-2020 [97, 98] and HIPE-2022 [99, 100] evaluation campaigns reviewed the most relevant datasets of historical and multilingual documents offering gold standard annotations for named entity recognition and linking. The most up-to-date output of this endeavour is the data released for the HIPE-2022 evaluation campaign, which comprises six Named Entities-annotated datasets consisting of historical newspapers and classic commentaries of 200 years time-span¹¹ in English, Finnish, French, German and Swedish. The data is sourced initially from various European cultural heritage projects, such as: (i) *NewsEye* ([101]), which provides historical newspaper articles in French, German, Finnish and Swedish dating back to 19C-20C; (ii) *SoNAR*, which includes historical newspaper articles from the Berlin State Library newspaper collections in German (19C-20C); (iii) *Le Temps*, which contains historical newspaper articles from two Swiss newspapers in French (19C-20C); (iv) *Living with Machines*, which has a dataset of historical newspaper articles from the British Library newspapers in English (18C-19C). HIPE-2022 data in English are the most relevant for our work. In HIPE-2022 data, the datasets that contain data in English are: 1. AJMC DATASET¹²; 2. TOPRES19TH¹³; 3. HIPE2020¹⁴. AJMC DATASET¹² contains a specific textual genre, *Classical Commentaries*, which diverges significantly from the textual genre contained in MHERCL v0.1. Also, the tagset employed in TOPRES19TH¹³ is highly specialised, focusing exclusively on toponyms. With MHERCL v0.1, we advance the SotA by introducing a dataset of annotated English data derived from a textual source that is not represented in HIPE-2022 (historical music periodicals). This distinct dataset enriches the current repository of available annotated resources. It captures a different set of named entities and types specific to a domain which diverges from those represented in HIPE-2022.

4.2.2. Models - general models and task specific models

4.2.2.1. Task Specific Models

The research in the field of Named Entity Recognition, Classification and Disambiguation was pioneered by [102] who proposed DIANED, a time-aware entity linking approach for diachronic corpora, which leverages KB-driven temporal information and text-driven temporal expressions. The HIPE-2022 evaluation campaign collates the most recent efforts in implementing models for NER and EL on historical documents. The most evident tendency that can be observed is that all the systems that participated in the competition used transformer-based approaches. The top ranking model on English language data, both for Named Entities Recognition and Entity Linking, has been proposed by [103, L3i] team. Their EL model builds upon the neural technique they introduced for CLEF-HIPE-2020 [104], enhanced with a filtering process to dissect and disambiguate historical references using Wikidata, described in [105]. Leveraging data from Wikipedia, Wikidata, and DBpedia provides a comprehensive entity analysis, aiding their method in accurately disambiguating mentions in historical documents.

¹¹<https://github.com/hipe-eval/HIPE-2022-data>

¹²<https://github.com/hipe-eval/HIPE-2022-data/blob/main/documentation/README-ajmc.md>

¹³<https://github.com/hipe-eval/HIPE-2022-data/blob/main/documentation/README-topres19th.md>

¹⁴<https://github.com/hipe-eval/HIPE-2022-data/blob/main/documentation/README-hipe2020.md>

4.2.2.2. General Models

Given the popularity of EL and the wide range of applications that involve this task, many new models have been recently proposed. Current research revolves mainly around PLM both for encoding mentions that are then used to compare and select candidates [9] and for directly generating entity identifiers conditioned on mentions in context [106]. [9] proposed BLINK, a BERT-based entity linking model. Given an entity mention, it retrieves potential candidates by embedding the mention and searching the most similar to this embedding in the embedding space of the descriptions of the entities of a KB. Each candidate is then re-ranked with a cross-encoder that concatenates the mention and entity text. A different approach, based on generative language models instead of classification architectures, was proposed in [107, GENRE]. This approach retrieves entities by generating their unique names, left to right, conditioned on the context. Such an approach directly captures relations between context and entity name and reduces the memory footprint of performing queries on large search spaces. An extension of this model was proposed in [106, mGENRE]. Also, in this case, the name of a target entity is generated in an autoregressive fashion. The only difference is that the model can be applied to different languages using a multilingual encoder and a multilingual KB.

4.3. The new benchmark for HEL

4.3.1. Background

4.3.1.1. The Polifonia Textual Corpus and Knowledge Extractor.

Figure 4.2: AMR graph resulting from the text2AMR parsing powered by [15, SPRING] of the sentence "A pleasing ballad, with fine melody, sung by Adelaide Phillips.", extrapolated from *Dwights Journal Of Music*, n. 12 (1868), part of the *Periodicals* module of the PTC¹⁵.

The MHERCL benchmark (v0.1) has been extrapolated from the Polifonia Textual Corpus (PTC)¹⁵, a multi-module, diachronic and multilingual corpus specialised on the music domain. MHERCL v0.1 sentences were processed through the Polifonia Knowledge Extractor (PKE)², a framework for extracting knowledge from contemporary and historical texts, which leverages as intermediate step Abstract Meaning Representation (AMR) [14], a popular formalism of natural language that represents the meaning of a sentence as a semantic graph, in which nodes represent concepts and edges represent relations among concepts. The sample is part of the *Filtered AMR Graphs Bank*²⁸.

An example of AMR graph, resulting from the text2AMR parsing powered by [15, SPRING] obtained via Text2AMR2FRED WebApp⁵ (cfr. Chapter 2 of this report) is reported in Figure 4.2. From the figure, it is possible to appreciate how the text2AMR parser module performs both NERC and EL ((z3 person

¹⁵<https://github.com/polifonia-project/Polifonia-Corpus>

:wiki "Adelaide_Phillipps":name (z4 name :op1 "Adelaide":op2 "Phillips")), the latter against Wikipedia as a KB.

4.3.1.2. Exploratory Study of Entity Linking Quality

Table 4.1: Table reporting statistics about the off-the-shelf quality of PKE² framework on EL of person Named Entities in a PTC sample.

#sents	person Named Entities (Superficial mention)		person Named Entities (Wikidata QID)		person Named Entities (Date of Birth)		
	#recognised	#linked	#found	#not found	#plausible	#not plausible	#not found
2205	2262	2108	2006	102	1199	203	604

As the PKE framework automatically recognises named entities in its text-to-AMR parsing step, we ran a preliminary experiment to evaluate the off-the-shelf performance of the PKE text-to-AMR parser ([15, SPRING]) and its embedded entity linker, [9, BLINK]. The results are reported in Table 4.1. We focused on a sample of 2205 sentences taken from the *Periodicals* module of the PTC and on named entities of type PERSON. In the selected sample, the PKE text-to-AMR parser ([15, SPRING]) identified 2262 instances of person Named Entities, 2108 of which were linked to a Wikipedia page by [9, BLINK]. We then tried to retrieve the correspondent Wikidata ID (QID) of the Wikipedia pages linked by [9, BLINK], to access the corresponding entity’s date of birth (DoB) through the Wikidata property P569 (*date of birth*). We could retrieve the QID of 2006 out of the 2108 Wikipedia pages linked by [9, BLINK].

Figure 4.3: AMR graph resulting from the text2AMR parsing powered by [15, SPRING] of the sentence "J.T. Imbault was born at Paris in 1753.", extrapolated from *The Quarterly Musical Magazine And Review*, n. 25 (1825), part of the *Periodicals* module of the PTC¹⁵.

J. T. Imbault

Figure 4.4: Screenshot of the Wikipedia page (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/J._T._Imbault) corresponding to the entity linked by [9, BLINK] in the sentence reported in Figure 4.3.

In the 102 cases where we could not retrieve a QID, the reason for the missed retrieval was that the entity linking was incorrect. This happened in cases in which the Wikipedia link pointed to a nonexistent Wikipedia page due to

hallucinations in the wikification process by [9, BLINK]. This hallucination occurs more often when the person Named Entities superficial mention in the text presents OCR errors, as shown in Figure 4.3. In the sentence, J.T. IMBAULT is the OCR-compromised superficial mention of J. J. Imbault, corresponding to Wikidata’s QID Q20538968. As we can see in Figure 4.4, [9, BLINK] links J.T. IMBAULT to a nonexistent Wikipedia page, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/J._T._Imbault.

Out of the 2006 retrieved QID, we could retrieve 1402 dates of birth: by comparing the retrieved DoB to the publication date of the periodicals in which the related mention of the person Named Entities occurred, we could verify that 1199 out of 1402 QIDs belonged to *plausible*¹⁶ named entities (namely, whose date of birth preceded that of the periodical issue) while 203 QIDs belonged to *not plausible* named entities (namely, whose date of birth followed that of the periodical issue). In the 604 cases in which we failed to retrieve a date of birth, the reason for the missed retrieval was that the entity linking was not correct (the Wikipedia page was not that of a person named entity, but that of a family name, a disambiguation page, etc.).

Checking the automatically retrieved person Named Entities entities against Wikidata’s knowledge base allowed us to assess that *at least*¹⁷ 909 out of the 2108 instances of person Named Entities entities’ Wikipedia pages linked by [9, BLINK] (43%) were wrong (Wikipedia pages for which we could not retrieve a related QID, or whose related QID was that of a person named entity whose date of birth (DoB) followed the date of issue of the periodical).

On contemporary text, [9, BLINK] scores an overall unnormalised accuracy of a minimum of 0.6825 on CLUEWEB - WNED-CWEB (CWEB) [108] to a maximum of 0.9087 on TAC-KBP 2010¹⁸, while according to the results of our exploratory studies its performance is much lower, indicating plenty of room for improvement on NERC and EL off-the-shelf models employed in the PKE² framework. Such an improvement can be achieved, among the other approaches, by fine-tuning the off-the-shelf models on historical data or by implementing custom filters to refine the off-the-shelf models’ output by leveraging knowledge, such as temporal and named entity’s type information stored in KBs such as Wikidata.

4.3.2. MHERCL v0.1 - Dataset Composition

4.3.2.1. Sampling

MHERCL v0.1 is made of manually annotated sentences extrapolated from the PTC¹⁵’s historical documents. This first release of the benchmark addressed a sample of the English *Periodicals*¹⁹ module of the corpus, whose documents’ publication dates range from 1823 to 1900. We have selected the sentences for the manual annotation based on four criteria: (1) Language (*English*); (2) Source (the *Periodicals* module of the PTC¹⁵) - we chose historical periodicals because of their similarity to historical newspapers, a textual genre at the centre of historical NERC and EL annotation campaigns (cfr. 4.2.1); (3) Being part of the *Filtered AMR Graphs Bank*²⁸ (filtered output of the PKE² framework); (4) Containing at least one named entity recognised by the PKE² framework²⁰.

We initiated our benchmark development with the *English* language due to its greater scope for comparison with other contemporary-text benchmarks, particularly in the context of model evaluation. We opted to extrapolate the sentences of MHERCL v0.1 from the *Periodicals* module of the PTC¹⁵ in order to align closely with the prevailing document types already utilised in existing benchmarks within the field. Historical newspaper is the dominant document type used in HIPE-2022 data [100]. We picked sentences that were part of our *Filtered AMR Graphs Bank*²⁸ to be able to contextually check the off-the-shelf NERC and EL predictions part of the AMR graphs output of the PKE² framework.

¹⁶In this Chapter, we use the term *plausible* to refer to person named entities whose date of birth, according to Wikidata, preceded that of the music periodical’s issue date. We use the term *not plausible* to refer to person named entities whose date of birth, according to Wikidata, followed that of the music periodical’s issue date.

¹⁷The person Named Entities entities’ Wikipedia pages linked by [9, BLINK] whose respective named entities’ QID had a plausible DoB can be either correct or wrong, so the total number of wrong entities can be higher.

¹⁸<https://catalog.ldc.upenn.edu/LDC2018T16>

¹⁹Full metadata of the *Periodicals* module of the Polifonia Textual Corpus are available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6671912>

²⁰In this report, it is assumed that this criterion has been used for sampling purposes. The sentences contained in MHERCL v0.1, in certain cases, do not contain any named entities.

4.3.2.2. Annotation Guidelines

The sentences included in the sample described in Paragraph 4.3.2.1 underwent manual annotations thanks to the work of two interns (Foreign Languages and Literature undergraduate students, both Italian native speakers, one graduating in English and Spanish Language and Literature, the other graduating in Russian and Spanish) that have received *ad hoc* training on the NERC and EL annotation task.

Generally, the annotation work was performed under the criteria that a named entity is a real-world thing indicating a unique individual through a proper noun [109]. The annotation work of the interns involved inspecting the sentences and identifying the named entities, eventually linking them to their corresponding Wikidata ID (QID).

Named entities were recognised, classified and linked following the AMR named entity annotations guidelines²¹. The types were assigned according to the AMR annotation guidance instructions²² and extrapolated from the AMR named entity types list²³.

A full description of the types used for NEs classification in MHERCL v0.1 is provided in A. Annotation guidelines are extensively described in Appendix B of this report.

4.3.2.3. IAA

Table 4.2: MHERCL v0.1 - Entity Linking IAA

#sents	#tokens (Tot.)	#tokens (Annotated)		Krippendorff's alpha
		#matching	#unmatching	
27	472	40	8	0,82

Inter-annotator agreement (IAA) measures the reliability of human annotations by estimating consistency among annotators. To measure IAA, we made two annotators independently annotate 27 sentences. We calculated *Krippendorff's alpha* [110] for nominal metric on the resulting annotations using Fast Krippendorff [111]. We opted for *Krippendorff's alpha* for its flexibility and resilience in handling missing values, as demonstrated by its successful usage in other contexts [112]. As reported in Table 4.2, we obtained the following result: 0.82654.

4.3.2.3.1. Error analysis In certain instances, the discrepancy can be attributed to the elevated complexity inherent to the case in question: the named entity mention occurring in the sentence is a historical name for that entity, used in the times in which the periodical from which the sentence is extrapolated was issued but not anymore in use in current times. Analysing two examples is interesting to understand the complexity of the EL task on historical documents. One case relates to the named entity mention *Court Magazine*, occurring in the sentence with text *I find the following sensible critical remarks among my papers; they were copied from a weekly work (the Court Magazine, I think)* and with ID *TheHarmonicon__1833-005.txt_1585*. One user assigned the label NIL to this named entity mention, while the other assigned the QID *Q3206551*²⁴, which relates to the Wikipedia page for *La Belle Assemblée*²⁵, in which we can read the following passage, which justifies the choice of assigning the QID *Q3206551*:

The magazine was published as La Belle Assemblée from 1806 until May 1832. It became The Court Magazine and Belle Assemblée from 1832 to 1837. After 1837 the Belle Assemblée name was dropped when the magazine merged with the Lady's Magazine and Museum (itself a merger of The Lady's Magazine and a competitor) to become The Court Magazine and Monthly Critic.

²¹<https://amr.isi.edu/doc/amr-dict.html#named%20entity>

²²<https://www.isi.edu/~ulf/amr/lib/popup/ne-type-selection.html>

²³<https://www.isi.edu/~ulf/amr/lib/ne-types.html>

²⁴<https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q3206551>

²⁵https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/La_Belle_Assembl%C3%A9e

The other is the case for the named entity mention `Court of Vienna`, occurring in the sentence with text *Sommer, organist to the Court of Vienna; this is the greatest compliment which can be paid to his talents.* and with ID `TheQuarterlyMusicalMagazineAndReview__1828-037.txt_1570`. One user assigned the label `NIL` to this named entity mention, while the other assigned the QID `Q209937`²⁶, which relates to the Wikipedia page for the *Vienna State Opera*²⁷, in which we can read the following passage:

The Vienna State Opera [...] is an opera house and opera company based in Vienna, Austria. [...] It was built from 1861 to 1869 following plans by August Sicard von Sicardsburg and Eduard van der Nüll, and designs by Josef Hlávka. The opera house was inaugurated as the "Vienna Court Opera" (Wiener Hofoper) in the presence of Emperor Franz Joseph I and Empress Elisabeth of Austria. It became known by its current name after establishing the First Austrian Republic in 1921.

The above passage misled the annotator who assigned the QID `Q209937`: in fact, the opera house was renowned with the name "Vienna Court Opera" after its building, which dates back to 1861-1869, which in any case is after the issue of the periodical that mentions it.

4.3.2.4. Statistics

Table 4.3: MHERCL v0.1 - Dataset Stats

Dataset	Lang.	#docs	#sents	#tokens
MHERCL v0.1	EN	21	715	15.734

Table 4.4: MHERCL v0.1 - Named Entities Superficial Mentions Stats

	#mention	#types	noisy	NIL
all	1.199	-	0,125	0,3403
unique	975	49	0,1527	0,4051

Table 4.5: Named entity types occurring in MHERCL v0.1

named entity type	#occurrences
person	621
city	143
music	68
country	42
organization	39
opera	38
building	29
work-of-art	28
road	22
publication	19

As summarised in Table 4.3, MHERCL v0.1 is made of 715 sentences, extrapolated from 21 documents (historical periodicals). As reported in Table 4.4, MHERCL v0.1 includes 975 unique named entities belonging to 49 different

²⁶<https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q209937>

²⁷https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Vienna_State_Opera

types. On the total of annotated named entity mentions, 34% could not be linked to a QID. Those are cases in which the annotators could not identify a Wikidata entry corresponding to the named entity mention. Those cases are annotated with the label NIL. On the total of annotated named entity mentions, 12,5% are *noisy*, namely impacted by errors due to OCR. Quantifying the noisy entities is important to facilitate downstream qualitative error analysis of NERC and EL systems and for comparison with other historical datasets [100].

Table 4.5 reports, in order of frequency, the top 10 NEs types occurring in MHERCL v0.1 . The types distribution reveals MHERCL v0.1 specificity to the music domain due to the presence of domain-specific types such as MUSIC, OPERA, WORK-OF-ART. A full description of the types used for NEs classification in MHERCL v0.1 is provided in Appendix A.

4.3.2.5. Format

MHERCL v0.1 is released in tab-separated values (TSV) files (UTF-8 encoded) through its dedicated GitHub repository²⁸. An example of an annotated sentence is reported below:

```
#document_id:DwightSJournalOfMusic__1873-016.txt_762
#document_date:1873
#sent_text:A native of Parma, ateighteen years of age Jong was received into
the Conservatory of Music of that town, where Jong soon made himself.a
name as the most promising pupil of the institution.
A      0      _      a      DET
native 0      _      native NOUN
of      0      _      of      ADP
Parma  B-city  Q2683  Parma  PROPN
,       0      _      ,       PUNCT
ateighteen 0      _      ateighteen NUM
years  0      _      year   NOUN
of      0      _      of      ADP
age     0      _      age     NOUN
'       0      _      '       PUNCT
Jong    B-person  NIL    Jong    PROPN
was     0      _      be      AUX
received 0      _      receive VERB
into    0      _      into    ADP
the     0      _      the     DET
Conservatory B-school  Q1439627 Conservatory PROPN
of      I-school  Q1439627 of      ADP
Music  I-school  Q1439627 Music  PROPN
of      0      _      of      ADP
that    0      _      that    DET
town    0      _      town    NOUN
,       0      _      ,       PUNCT
where   0      _      where   SCONJ
'       0      _      '       PUNCT
Jong    B-person  NIL    Jong    PROPN
soon    0      _      soon    ADV
made    0      _      make    VERB
himself.a 0      _      himself.a PRON
name    0      _      name    NOUN
as      0      _      as      ADP
the     0      _      the     DET
```

²⁸https://github.com/polifonia-project/historical-entity-linking/blob/main/benchmark/v0.1/mhercl_v01.tsv

most	O	—	most	ADV		
promising		O	—	promising	ADJ	
pupil	O	—	pupil	NOUN		
of	O	—	of	ADP		
the	O	—	the	DET		
institution		O	—	institution	NOUN	
.	O	—	.	PUNCT		

In the above example, we can see that rows beginning with # contain metadata. In more details:

- #DOCUMENT_ID, provides the PTC¹⁵'s ID of the document the sentence is extrapolated from;
- #DOCUMENT_DATE, provides the date in which the document was published;
- #SENT_TEXT, provides the text of the annotated sentence.

. The columns can be explained as follows:

- COLUMN 0 reports the sentence's tokens, one per row;
- COLUMN 1, reports BIO²⁹ tags and type label of the named entity;
- COLUMN 2, reports the Wikidata QID assigned by the annotators to the identified named entity;
- COLUMN 3, reports the token's base form (lemma);
- COLUMN 4, reports the token's Part of Speech (PoS) tag.

MHERCL v0.1 format has been designed to comply with HIPE-2022 data (which is based on IOB and CoNLL-U), facilitating future integration.

4.4. ELD

Our approach to EL assumes that the disambiguation process underlying this task has to be coherent with the context in which entities appear, respecting time and logical constraints. To this end, we developed ELD (Entity Linking Dynamics), an innovative model that is grounded on relaxation labelling processes [113]. This class of algorithms can produce consistent labelling of the data thanks to the use of constraints among labels designed to make the label assigned to an object consistent with the labels assigned to the other objects in the same batch. Relaxation labeling processes have been used successfully on different fields, including computer vision [96], NLP [114] and graph processing [115]. Relaxation labelling has also been formulated in terms of game theory [116] by interpreting the objects to be labelled as the players of a non-cooperative game [117] and the constraints on labels as the strategies that the players can select to play the game. We recall here that in game theory, the players are considered rational and select the strategy that maximises a predefined payoff. The selection is performed considering the strategies a co-player can select in response to a strategy.

Table 4.6: An example of a payoff matrix for the game of matching pennies. The number on the left of each cell of the matrix indicates the payoff obtained by player 1, and the number on the right indicates the payoff of player 2. Player 1 plays according to the rows of the matrix, and player 2 with the columns.

		PLAYER 2	
		heads	tails
PLAYER 1	heads	1 -1	-1 1
	tails	-1 1	-1 -1

This information is stored in a payoff matrix (see Table 4.6) that defines the game. In this example, it is defined as the game of matching pennies, in which player 1 wins if both players select the same face of the penny and player 2

²⁹According to BIO notation tagging format, each token which constitutes the beginning of a named entity string is assigned the label 'B' (an abbreviation of 'beginning'). Each token which falls within a named entity string is assigned the label 'I' (an abbreviation for 'inside'). Each token standing outside of a named entity string is assigned the label 'O' (an abbreviation for 'outside').

wins if both players do not select the same face. The top left cell of the payoff matrix depicts the situation in which player 1 selects heads and player 2 selects heads. The outcome of this game is a payoff of 1 for player 1 and a payoff of -1 for player 2. As it can be seen, the outcome of a game does not depend on the strategy selected by a single player but on the combination of the strategies selected by the players involved in the game.

More formally, game dynamics consists of a finite set of players $N = (1, \dots, n)$, a finite set of pure strategies $S_i = \{1, \dots, m_i\}$ for each player $i \in N$, and a payoff (utility) function $u_i : S \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, that associates a payoff with each combination of strategies in $S = S_1 \times S_2 \times \dots \times S_n$. A player i , in addition to playing single (pure) strategies from S_i , can also use mixed strategies, that are probability distributions over pure strategies. In A mixed strategy over S_i is defined as a vector $\mathbf{x}_i = (x_1, \dots, x_{m_i})$, such that $x_j \geq 0$ and $\sum x_j = 1$. Each mixed strategy corresponds to a point in the simplex Δ_{m_i} , whose corners correspond to pure strategies. The intuition is that player i randomises over strategies according to the probabilities in x_i . Each mixed strategy profile lives in the mixed strategy space of the game, given by the Cartesian product $\Theta = \Delta_{m_1} \times \Delta_{m_2} \times \dots \times \Delta_{m_n}$. In a two-player game, a strategy profile can be defined as a pair (x_i, x_j) . The expected payoff for this strategy profile is computed as:

$$u(x_i, x_j) = \mathbf{x}_i^\top \cdot A_{ij} x_j, \quad (4.1)$$

where A_{ij} is the $m_i \times m_j$ payoff matrix between players i and j . I mixed strategy for the game of matching pennies is to play heads and tails with the same probability. In this way, it would be difficult for the co-player to guess the strategy that will be played.

The payoff corresponding to the h -th pure strategy is computed as:

$$u(\mathbf{x}_i) = \mathbf{x}_i \cdot \sum_{j=1}^{n_i} (A_{ij} x_j)^h, \quad (4.2)$$

this payoff is additively separable. The summation is over all the n_i players with whom i is playing. The average payoff of player i is calculated as:

$$u(\mathbf{x}_i) = \sum_{h=1}^{m_i} u(x_i^h). \quad (4.3)$$

To find the Nash equilibrium of the game, that corresponds to a situation in which each player is playing his best mixed strategy, it is common to use the discrete time version of the replicator dynamics equation [118] for each player $i \in N$,

$$x_i^h(t+1) = x_i^h(t) \frac{u(x_i^h)}{u(\mathbf{x}_i)} \forall h \in \mathbf{x}_i \quad (4.4)$$

This equation allows better-than-average strategies to grow at each iteration. It can be considered an inductive learning process in which the players learn from past experiences how to play their best strategy.

4.4.1. Implementation

The EL task is modeled in ELD performing at the same time also the Word Sense Disambiguation (WSD). This formulation of the problem allows the exploitation of contextual information to perform consistent data labelling, disambiguating entities and considering nouns and verbs around them. As we will see later, it is possible to model EL and WSD together thanks to a shared vector space for the computation of the feature vectors of both tasks.

The pipeline of our model is presented in Figure 4.5. ELD takes as input a text that is pre-processed with a tokeniser, a part-of-speech tagger and a named entity recognition tagger to obtain a set of annotations $T = ((t_1, pos_1, ner_1), (t_2, pos_2, ner_2), \dots, (t_n, pos_n, ner_n))$ (step 1). In addition to this annotation, the text is also fed into a Language Model to obtain a contextualised representation of each token $E = (e_1, e_2, \dots, e_n)$, since the tokenisations in T and E are different (E uses subtokens), we average the subtoken representations in E to match the tokenisation in T (step 2). This step allows to obtain a feature vector for each token in T , which results in a

Figure 4.5: The pipeline of ELD. Vectors with red borders represent the strategy space distribution of an entity. It is updated at each iteration of the system, calculating the payoff that each strategy (entity id) obtains playing with all its neighbours, both entities (player j in this example) and non-entity words (player k and z in this example) represented with blue border vectors. Once the payoffs are computed, the vector of player i is normalised to obtain a new distribution used at the system's next iteration. This update is performed for all the players at each iteration of the system until it converges.

$n \times w$ matrix W in which only the n nouns, verbs, adjectives, adverbs and named entities in T are maintained (w refers to the number of dimensions of the feature vectors). These n tokens are the players of the game dynamics implemented in ELD. With the embedding matrix W , it is possible to create the $n \times n$ matrix A that encodes pairwise similarity information among each embedding in W . This information will be used by ELD to weigh each player's influence on another in a way in which similar players have a more considerable reciprocal influence in the strategy selection. For example, in the following sentence:

1. Abe Lincoln played the guitar in the Dinosaurs band for 20 years.

the word *guitar* can influence more than the word *years* the linking of the mention *Abe Lincoln* toward the entity *Abe_Lincoln_(guitarist)* than towards the entity *Abe_Lincoln_(politician)*.

Once the tokenisations are obtained, the candidate generation is performed in step 3, i.e., selecting the possible senses/entities to which a word/mention can refer. For this operation, we used two different knowledge bases: WordNet for the selection of the senses of nouns, verbs, adjectives and adverbs, and Wikidata for the selection of entities connected to a mention marked as named entity. With this information it is possible to define the m_i strategies that each player i can select as $S_i = (s_1, s_2, \dots, s_{m_i})$. The single strategy spaces allow to create the strategy space of the game as the set of different strategies of each player $S = s_1, s_2, \dots, s_m$. This information is then used to create other two matrices used by ELD. The first one is the $n \times m$ matrix X that represents the strategy space of the game as a probability distribution. Each player uses the resulting probability vector as a mixed strategy with m elements (strategies not in the strategy space of a player have 0 probability). The strategy space can be initialised using a uniform distribution with the following equation:

$$x_i^h = \begin{cases} |m_i|^{-1} & \text{if sense/entity } h \text{ is in } S_i, \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (4.5)$$

or with a prior if it is available, substituting $|m_i|^{-1}$ in Equation 4.5 with the frequency of the corresponding sense/entity and normalising x_i to make it sum up to 1.

The second one is the $m \times d$ matrix D in which each sense/entity is represented as an embedding. To make sense

of entity embedding, we used embeddings created with the same methodology to have them both in the same vector space. Sense embedding is obtained using Ares embeddings [119] that employs a multilingual language model to embed text annotated with WSD information and to combine the resulting representations for each distinct sense. We followed the same procedure to develop the entity embeddings, embedding text annotated with EL information with the same multilingual language model used by Ares, i.e., mBERT [120]. With the embedding matrix D , it is possible to create the $m \times m$ matrix Z that encodes pairwise similarity information among each embedding in D . This matrix represents the payoff matrix of the games so that the payoff is higher if two senses/entities are similar. This operation will allow to maintain the textual coherence and to force players to select strategies that are related, such as the sense of *guitar* as a musical instrument and an musician entity or two entities that are contemporary or connected such as a composer and his instructor.

Once these sources of information are computed, ELD can be started by using the replicator dynamic equation [121] in Equation 4.4, where the payoff of strategy h for player i is calculated as:

$$u(x_i^h) = x_i^h \cdot \sum_{j=1}^{n_i} (A_{ij} Z \mathbf{x}_j)^h \quad (4.6)$$

where n_i are the neighbours of player i as in the graph A . The average payoff is calculated as:

$$u(\mathbf{x}_i) = \sum_{h=1}^{m_i} u(x_i^h) \quad (4.7)$$

Table 4.7: Datasets Stats

	set	#docs	#tokens	# entities	noisy	NIL
MHERCL	v0.1	20	15.734	1.199	0,125	0,34
HIPE2020	test	46	16.635	449	0,0557	0,402

4.5. Experimental setup

4.5.1. Datasets

The evaluation of ELD is performed on two datasets: HIPE-2022 and our newly released benchmark MHERCL v0.1. On the overall multilingual HIPE-2022 data³⁰, for the scope of this deliverable, we concentrate only on the data in English language, because MHERCL v0.1 includes only English language text. AJMC DATASET¹² and *Classical Commentaries* textual genres diverge significantly from the ones contained in MHERCL v0.1. Also, the tagset used in TOPRES19TH¹³ is very narrow, focusing exclusively on toponyms. Consequently, we opted to include in our experiments only the English data released within HIPE2020¹⁴.

The statistics of MHERCL v0.1 and English data of HIPE2020¹⁴ are presented in Table 4.7.

4.5.2. Models

Our evaluation was conducted comparing the results of three models: ELD, [9, BLINK] and the model proposed by [103, L3i]. The model proposed by [103, L3i], as described in Section 4.2.2.1, is the model that ranked higher in CLEF-HIPE-2022 for the Entity Linking task on HIPE2020 English data. ELD and BLINK can be considered as general models. For this reason, we implemented five versions for them, with different candidate retention functionalities that we describe in the paragraphs below.

³⁰<https://github.com/hipe-eval/HIPE-2022-data/tree/main>

4.5.2.1. Functionalities

Table 4.8: Time-related Wikidata properties used for candidate retention functionalities

Retrieval Order	Wikidata property	Name	Description
1	P569	DATE OF BIRTH	date on which the subject was born
2	P571	INCEPTION	time when an entity begins to exist
3	P1619	DATE OF OFFICIAL OPENING	date or point in time an event, museum, theater etc. officially opened
4	P1191	DATE OF FIRST PERFORMANCE	date a work was first debuted, performed or live-broadcasted
5	P10135	RECORDING DATE	the date when a recording was made
6	P577	PUBLICATION DATE	date or point in time when a work was first published or released
7	P575	TIME OF DISCOVERY OR INVENTION	date or point in time when the item was discovered or invented
8	P1317	FLORUIT	date when the person was known to be active or alive, when birth or death not documented
9	P7124	DATE OF THE FIRST ONE	qualifier: when the first element of a quantity appeared/took place
10	P10673	DEBUT DATE	date when a person or group is considered to have "debuted"
11	P9448	INTRODUCED ON	date when a bill was introduced into a legislature
12	P6949	ANNOUNCEMENT DATE	time of the first public presentation of a subject by the creator, of information by the media
13	P729	SERVICE ENTRY	date or point in time on which a piece or class of equipment entered operational service
14	P2031	WORK PERIOD (START)	start of period during which a person or group flourished (fl. = "floruit") in their professional activity
15	P585	POINT IN TIME	time and date something took place, existed or a statement was true

4.5.2.1.1. Time The first criterion upon which we based our candidate retention functionalities is the comparison between (a) MHERCL v0.1, or HIPE-2020, documents' date of publication, which are given as metadata in the datasets; (b) the information extracted by retrieving the value of the time-related Wikidata properties labels per candidate. If (b) chronologically follows (a), the candidate is filtered out from the list by the model that has this functionality activated. We report the time-related Wikidata properties that we considered in our experiments in Table 4.8. The properties' retrieval order has been set according to a qualitative analysis of the semantics of the properties' names and descriptions. The analysis aimed to ensure to retain, when available, the most precise properties' values, such as P569 - DATE OF BIRTH (ranked first), against less precise ones, such as P585 - POINT IN TIME (ranked last).

4.5.2.1.2. Type The second criterion upon which we based our candidate retention functionalities is the comparison between (a) the gold NER class (*type*) assigned to the superficial named entity mentioned by the human annotators (for details about the types used in MHERCL v0.1, see Appendix A; for details about the types used in HIPE-2020, see [99, 100]); (b) the *types* extracted by retrieving the value of P31 - 'INSTANCE OF' Wikidata property's labels per candidate. Mapping rules between (a) and (b) were established. If (a) is not included in (b), the candidate is filtered out from the list by the model that has this functionality activated.

4.5.2.2. Settings

The functionalities were activated or deactivated to assess which component contributes more to the performance of the model:

1. MODEL_{DOT}. In this case, the model simply computes the similarity among the embedding of a mention with the embeddings of its candidates and the candidate with the highest similarity is selected as the entity to link to the mention;
2. MODEL_{ALL}. For ELD, the payoff is computed as described in Section 4.4.1 and all candidates retrieved from a Wikidata are retained. Also for [9, BLINK] the candidates are not filtered;
3. MODEL_{TIME}. It corresponds to MODEL_{ALL}, but, in this case, only the candidates with a date (cfr. Table 4.8) posterior to the publication year of the document under analysis are retained³¹.

³¹This candidate retention policy is not applied to superficial named entity mentions whose NER class suggests that the entity is a location, namely CITY, CITY-DISTRICT, COUNTRY, ROAD, SQUARE, COUNTY, LOCAL-REGION, CONTINENT, MOUNTAIN, COUNTRY-REGION, PROVINCE for MHERCL v0.1, and LOC for HIPE-2022.

4. $MODEL_{TYPE}$. It corresponds to $MODEL_{ALL}$, but, in this case, only the candidates that share the same NER class with the one annotated in the benchmarks are retained³.
5. $MODEL_{TIME-TYPE}$. It corresponds to $MODEL_{ALL}$, but, in this case, both dates and types are considered to filter the candidate list³.

4.6. Results and Analysis

In this section, we will present our evaluation on MHERCL and HIPE.

Table 4.9: MHERCL. The results are provided as Precision, Recall and F1. The highest value in the Precision column is in bold and the first result with a statistically significant difference from it is marked with * ($\chi^2, p < 0.05$)

Model	Precision	Recall	F1 measure
$BLINK_{DOT}$	0,51	0,76	0,61
$BLINK_{ALL}$	0,51	0,77	0,62
$BLINK_{TIME}$	0,53	0,77	0,63
$BLINK_{TYPE}$	0,57	0,75	0,65
$BLINK_{TIME-TYPE}$	0,61	0,75	0,68
ELD_{DOT}	0.50	0.5	0.5
ELD_{ALL}	0.56	0.56	0.56
ELD_{TIME}	0.56	0.56	0.56
ELD_{TYPE}	0.57*	0.57	0.57
$ELD_{TIME-TYPE}$	0.57*	0.57	0.57

4.6.1. MHERCL

The results of our evaluation on MHERCL are presented in Table 4.9 as Precision, Recall and F1. The first consideration that we can make is that the DOT models have the lowest performances. However, when BLINK uses all the candidates, it is not able to improve this result, indicating that this model heavily relies on the candidate ranking provided by the candidate retriever. On the contrary, the disambiguation dynamics operated by ELD can increase the results by 6 points, indicating that the consistent labelling of the entities in a sentence benefits the task. Using the temporal filter (TIME) allows BLINK to increase its performances but does not affect ELD. This is probably due to the candidate set used by BLINK that is based on latent representations and allows the obtainment a large set of candidates (30) even in case of spelling errors. Refining this list with the temporal filter allows for discarding implausible entities that, if retained, would have ranked high. The candidate selection used by ELD depends on look-up tables that require the mention to be correct and included in them to retrieve candidates. Hence, the candidate set obtained with our model could be smaller, so the temporal filter does not have the desired impact on its performance. The filter on entity types (TYPE) improves the performances of both models. Also in this case, the boost is higher for [9, BLINK], indicating once again that the procedure used by this model to obtain candidates is effective. Combining the two filters allows [9, BLINK] to increase its performances further, confirming that using filters is beneficial. Considering also Recall and F1, we can observe that [9, BLINK] is a high recall model and that this allows to increase also the F1 score. ELD instead, has the same Precision, Recall and F1 because it always provides an answer, and this affects the F1 score. The lessons that we learnt from this experiment are: (i) time and type filters are effective solutions for HEL; (ii) the candidate selection performed by [9, BLINK] is a valid tool to overcome limitations related to spelling errors and linguistic variations; (iii) a large set of candidates is useful in combination with filters; (iv) the contextual disambiguation performed by ELD is effective for HEL.

Table 4.10: HIPE2020. The results are provided as Precision, Recall and F1. The highest value in the Precision column is in bold, and the first result with a statistically significant difference from it is marked with * ($\chi^2, p < 0.05$)

Model	Precision	Recall	F1 measure
L3i[103]	0,54	0,54	0,54
BLINK _{DOT}	0,34	0,59	0,43
BLINK _{ALL}	0,33	0,58	0,42
BLINK _{TIME}	0,36	0,60	0,45
BLINK _{TYPE}	0,40	0,59	0,48
BLINK _{TIME-TYPE}	0,42	0,60	0,49
ELD _{DOT}	0.46*	0.46	0.46
ELD _{ALL}	0.62	0.62	0.62
ELD _{TIME}	0.63	0.63	0.63
ELD _{TYPE}	0.61	0.61	0.61
ELD _{TIME-TYPE}	0.61	0.61	0.61

4.6.2. HIPE

The results of our evaluation on HIPE are presented in Table 4.10 as Precision, Recall and F1. Our first observation is that on this dataset, the performances of BLINK are lower compared to those obtained on MHERCL v0.1. However, they follow the same pattern with a beneficial effect given by our filters. An in-depth error analysis is required to investigate the reasons behind this relatively low performance, and we will follow-up on that in our final deliverable (D4.7 Evaluation of multilingual corpora and knowledge extraction methods).

The score of the model by L3i[103] team (the best-performing model at CLEF-HIPE 2022 competition) on this dataset is 0.54, which is well below the score obtained by the highest score obtained by ELD. Also, in this experiment, the filters do not significantly impact our model, and the TYPE filter decreases the performances of the model without filters and with the time filter only. This is likely due to the noisy information we obtain from Wikidata, and suggest that this data must be further analyzed, refining the mapping with HIPE-2022 NERC classes (types) and correct this aspect to exploit the filters' potential.

4.7. Conclusion

In this chapter, we presented MHERCL v0.1, a collection of annotated English sentences for historical named entity recognition, classification and linking. The dataset is available to the research community for further study. It is derived from historical periodicals published between 1823 and 1900 collected within the building of the Polifonia Textual Corpus², a multilingual, multi-module and diachronic corpus on Musical Heritage. For future work, we plan to expand the dataset by including annotated sentences extrapolated from Italian historical periodicals specialised in the music domain. To the best of our knowledge, there is no recently released resource of historical periodicals in Italian with annotations for the NERC and EL tasks, so contributing with a specialised benchmark in this language would significantly contribute to the community. This planned expansion of our benchmark will be released in our final deliverable (D4.7 Evaluation of multilingual corpora and knowledge extraction methods). Also, in collaboration with musicologists, we will validate the NEs that the annotators could not link to Wikidata and consider adding them as new entries to that KB.

We presented and evaluated also a new model for HEL and two simple methods to improve the quality of entity linking results based on temporal and typological filters. The model evaluation allowed us to identify some weaknesses and propose solutions for improvements. First of all, we can see that the method used by BLINK to retrieve candidates is more effective than ours. For this reason, the next evaluation of the model that will be conducted in the final deliverable of our WP will include a ELD a candidate retriever similar to the one used by BLINK. Furthermore, since temporal and typological filters have been demonstrated to be beneficial, we aim to improve the quality of the data we

used for this operation to possibly use it on a larger domain. Another aspect of the model that can be improved is the increase of its Recall, using a procedure that allows the model not to answer when there is not sufficient information. All these features will be implemented and tested for our final deliverable (D4.7 Evaluation of multilingual corpora and knowledge extraction methods).

4.7.1. Software and Data Release

We collect in this subsection the main software and data resources of MHERCL v0.1 and ELD mentioned in Section 4 of this deliverable. Details about their compliance with the FAIR protocol is reported in Chapter 5 of this report.

- MHERCL v0.1 and ELD - Available at <https://github.com/polifonia-project/historical-entity-linking>.

5. FAIR Protocol

We have implemented a number of actions to ensure that these outputs are in compliance with the FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship [122]. The outputs released as a result of the work described in this deliverable (all code, data, and related resources), summarised in Section 5.1 of this Chapter, are available online at their respective GitHub repositories. The latest versions of the outputs are available on Zenodo, in synchronisation with GitHub releases for consistent versioning. Via GitHub and Zenodo, the outputs have a unique and persistent identifier and is registered in a searchable source.

5.1. Overall Software and Data Release Summary for FAIR Protocol Section

- **Text2AMR2FRED** (cfr. Chapter 2 of this deliverable):
 - Polifonia Knowledge Extractor - Available at <https://github.com/polifonia-project/Polifonia-Knowledge-Extractor>. It has been released on Zenodo¹. Its persistent URI (DOI) is 10.5281/zenodo.7034505².
 - AMR2FRED - Available at <https://github.com/polifonia-project/amr2Fred>. It has been released on Zenodo³. Its persistent URI (DOI) is 10.5281/zenodo.8369929⁴.
 - Text2AMR2FRED API - Available at: <http://framester.istc.cnr.it/txt-amr-fred/api/docs/>.
 - Text2AMR2FRED WebApp - Available at: <https://arco.istc.cnr.it/txt-amr-fred/>.
 - Machine Reading suite - Available at: <https://github.com/polifonia-project/machine-reading>. It has been released on Zenodo. Its persistent URI (DOI) is 10.5281/zenodo.8370103⁵.
 - MusicBO Knowledge Graph - Available at: <https://github.com/polifonia-project/musicbo-knowledge-graph>. Its persistent URI (DOI) is 10.5281/zenodo.7654753⁶.
 - MusicBO Knowledge Graph SPARQL endpoint - Available at: <https://polifonia.disi.unibo.it/musicbo/sparql>.
 - MusicBO Knowledge Graph MELODY data story - Available at: https://projects.dharc.unibo.it/melody/musicbo/music_in_bologna_knowledge_graph_overview.
 - AMR evaluation web tool - Available at: <http://framester.istc.cnr.it/amr-eval>.
 - Comparison with Large Language Models - Proof-of-Concept Study - Available at: <https://github.com/polifonia-project/llms-vs-specialised-knowledge>. Its persistent URI (DOI) is 10.5281/zenodo.8396416⁷.
- **OCR post-correction** (cfr. Chapter 3 of this deliverable):
 - Software and data resources of tools for POC mentioned in Section 3 - Available at <https://github.com/polifonia-project/generative-post-ocr-correction>. Its persistent URI (DOI) is

¹<https://zenodo.org/>

²<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7034505>

³<https://zenodo.org/>

⁴<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8369929>

⁵<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8370103>

⁶<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7654753>

⁷<https://zenodo.org/badge/latestdoi/698869883>

10.5281/zenodo.8396855⁸.

- **Historical Entity Linking** (cfr. Chapter 4 of this deliverable):

- MHERCL v0.1 and ELD - Available at <https://github.com/polifonia-project/historical-entity-linking>. Its persistent URI (DOI) is 10.5281/zenodo.8396799⁹.

Through the addition of YAML metadata according to the Polifonia Ecosystem rulebook¹⁰, all outputs are also integrated within the Ecosystem automatically through its future releases with well-described, machine-processable metadata from various interoperable schemas. Furthermore, being integrated as part of the Polifonia Ecosystem, all data and metadata produced use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation.

Licensing. All the outputs presented in this deliverable follow the guidelines and the recommendations in the Polifonia Data Management Plan. All outputs listed in Section 5.1 of this Chapter are made available under CC-BY 4.0.

Sustainability and preservation plan. All outputs listed in Section 5.1 of this Chapter is under version control on public GitHub repositories (c.f. Section 5.1 of this Chapter), and all repositories are also published on Zenodo (with associated DOIs). The storage of all resources on GitHub guarantees their persistence beyond the project.

Documentation. While improving and extending our contributions, we have also invested efforts on producing high quality documentation for our resources. Each software and data release GitHub repository created for this deliverable has a clear and well-structured README where all the preliminary information that are necessary to understand the domain and the goals of the outputs are provided upfront.

⁸<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8396855>

⁹<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8396799>

¹⁰<https://github.com/polifonia-project/rulebook>

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A. Appendix A

A.1. Named Entities Classification in MHERCL v0.1

A.1.1. Named Entities Types

The types assigned to Named Entities (NEs) in MHERCL v0.1 are selected from the AMR named entity types list¹. We report them in the bullet list below:

- person, family, animal, language, nationality, ethnic-group, regional-group, religious-group, political-movement
- organization, company, government-organization, military, criminal-organization, political-party, market-sector school, university, research-institute, team, league
- location, city, city-district, county, state, province, territory, country, local-region, country-region, world-region, continent
- ocean, sea, lake, river, gulf, bay, strait, canal peninsula, mountain, volcano, valley, canyon, island, desert, forest, moon, planet, star, constellation
- facility, airport, station, port, tunnel, bridge, road, railway-line, canal building, theater, museum, palace, hotel, worship-place, sports-facility, market, park, zoo, amusement-park
- event, incident, natural-disaster, earthquake, war, conference, game, festival
- product, vehicle, ship, aircraft, aircraft-type, spaceship, car-make, work-of-art, picture, music, show, broadcast-program
- publication, book, newspaper, magazine, journal
- natural-object
- award, law, court-decision, treaty, music-key², musical-note², food-dish, writing-script, variable, program

In Table A.1, we report all the entity types assigned to NEs in MHERCL v0.1.

¹<https://www.isi.edu/~ulf/amr/lib/ne-types.html>

²We decided not to annotate music-key and musical-notes as entities because they do not correspond to real-world things indicating a unique individual

Table A.1: Named entity types occurring in MHERCL v0.1

named entity type	#occurrences
person	621
city	143
music	68
country	42
organization	39
opera	38
building	29
work-of-art	28
road	22
publication	19
worship-place	19
book	14
theatre	12
city-district	11
company	9
nan	9
school	7
theater	7
university	5
magazine	4
government-organization	4
festival	3
college	3
street	3
facility	3
local-region	3
museum	3
symphony	2
square	2
newspaper	2
concert	2
county	2
person	2
mountain	2
religious-group	2
persona	1
thing	1
empire	1
hotel	1
state	1
event	1
province	1
country-region	1
military	1
song	1
institution	1
person (fictional character)	1
continent	1
journal	1
language	1
Grand total	59 1199

B. Appendix B

B.1. Annotation Guidelines for the Musical Heritage Historical named Entities Recognition, Classification and Linking benchmark (MHERCL v0.1)

B.1.1. Annotation Tool

- We developed and used an *ad hoc* tool, available on the Web, specifically designed for serving a two-fold purpose: 1. annotating and linking Named Entities (NEs) occurring in the *Periodicals* module of the PTC¹; 2. assessing the correctness of NEs recognition, classification (NERC) and Entity Linking (EL) performed off-the-shelf by the text2AMR step of our Text2AMR2FRED⁵⁴ module. As extensively reported in Chapters 2 and 4 of this report, in the text2AMR step of Text2AMR2FRED, NEs recognition and classification is performed by SPRING [15] and EL by BLINK [9]. The tool will be described in this Appendix by reporting screenshots.

B.1.1.1. Note on Annotations Tool Screenshots and Examples

- To illustrate the full range of annotation tool functionalities, screenshots and examples may intentionally include incorrect predictions by SPRING [15] and BLINK [9] of named entity recognition, classification, and linking. These are included to provide a comprehensive overview of how the tool allows the annotators to enter a rich annotation input in the Annotation Tool.

B.2. Named Entity Recognition (NER) and Entity Linking (EL) Annotation Guidelines

B.2.1. Named Entity Recognition (NER)

Figure B.1: NLP pipeline introduction for the annotators of MHERCL v0.1.

B.2.1.1. General guidelines

- The annotators were instructed to consider a named entity a real-world thing indicating a unique individual through a proper noun [109]. The annotators were given a brief introduction to a typical NLP pipeline (tokenization, part-of-speech tagging, word sense disambiguation, named entities recognition and entity linking), with special emphasis on the Named Entities Recognition (NER) and Entity Linking (EL) tasks. In Figure B.1, we can see the slide used to support these general guidelines for the annotators.
- *Nested entities*. The annotators were instructed not to annotate nested NE. In cases such as *Account of the Oxford Commemoration Concerts*, the only valid named entity would be the "main" one (in our example, the entity of type PUBLICATION *Account of the Oxford Commemoration Concerts*). Therefore, in our example, "Oxford" would not be annotated as an entity of type CITY.

B.2.1.2. Example in the Annotation Tool

Sentence #47 (BLEURT: 1) Dwight's Journal of Music_1855-002_ms_1

And in the beautiful galleries of the Prince Es sterhdzy, (that munificent patron | of: Art) one can, at least, recall in imagination some- strains of the choice chamber music. of, Beethoven, to which their walls echoed in the presence of the great master, and in his palmiest days. os se I was much impressed by the fine monument of the Archduchess Christina, by Canova, which stands in the Church of the Augustines.

Figure B.2: NER - Example in the Annotation Tool

- As we can see in Figure B.2, the annotator can assess whether the NER performed off-the-shelf by the text2AMR parser [15] employed in our Text2AMR2FRED⁵⁴ module (cfr. 2) is correct or not. If it is incorrect (as in the case of the Figure), the annotator is requested to record the NE superficial mention with and without OCR errors. This strategy has allowed us to keep track of how many NE superficial mentions were *noisy*, namely impacted by OCR errors.

B.2.2. Named Entity Classification (NEC)

B.2.2.1. General guidelines

- The types were assigned according to the AMR annotation guidance instructions¹ and selected from the AMR named entity types list². Sticking to the AMR annotation guidance instructions, the annotators were instructed to select the most specific type possible.

¹<https://www.isi.edu/~ulf/amr/lib/popup/ne-type-selection.html>

²<https://www.isi.edu/~ulf/amr/lib/ne-types.html>

B.2.2.2. Example in the Annotation Tool

- In the Annotation Tool, if the NE type predicted by SPRING [15] and BLINK [9] was wrong, the annotator could choose the correct type from a drop-down list.

B.2.3. Entity Linking (EL)

B.2.3.1. General guidelines

Figure B.3: EL - General guidelines

- The annotators were instructed to link the named entities recognized to their corresponding Wikidata ID (QID). In Figure B.3, we can see the slide used to support these general guidelines for the annotators.
- The annotators were instructed to assign a QID only if the context of the annotated sentence was sufficient for a human reader to disambiguate the entity. The annotators were instructed to annotate the named entity recognized with the string NIL if the context was insufficient.
- The annotators were instructed to assign the string NIL also to named entities not present in Wikidata.

B.2.3.2. Example in the Annotation Tool

- As we can see in Figure B.4, the annotator can assess whether the EL performed off-the-shelf by BLINK [9], the entity linker employed in the text2AMR parser [15] included in our Text2AMR2FRED⁵⁴ module (cfr. 2) is correct or not. If it is incorrect, (as in the case of the Figure), the annotator is requested to record the correct Wikipedia page link and Wikidata QID.

B.2.4. Missing Named Entities

B.2.4.1. General guidelines

- The annotators were instructed to carefully scrutinize each sentence to ensure that no named entities were entirely overlooked by the by BLINK [9], the entity linker employed in the text2AMR parser [15] included in our Text2AMR2FRED⁵⁴ module (cfr. 2) tool.

Sentence #49 (BLEURT: 1) Dwight's Journal of Music_1855-002_ms_3

Below **Schandau** you pass the bold promontory of Schramstein, close sunder the fortified heights of Pfaffenstein, and 'Konigstein with its impregnable fortress—against whose walls Napoleon battered: in vain—thence on, through a wild country of tale-telling tradition, "thé cradle of gnomes and kobolds," till, at length, near Dresden you emerge among thriving . Villages and cultivated fields; like the exit, on the Neckar, from the vallies of Odenwald upon the plains of the Rhine at Heidelberg.

Missing named entities

Report the name of any named entity that you think is present in the text but is missing in the AMR graph

Leave the corresponding field(s) empty to remove an entity; empty fields are ignored

Entity name or mention (without OCR errors)

Entity name or mention (with OCR errors, if relevant)

Entity type

Wikipedia page (if it exists)

Wikidata QID (if it exists)

Figure B.5: Missing Named Entities - Example in the Annotation Tool